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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab
JRAs	Joint Research Activities
LLL	Living Lab Lexicon
IRL	Innovation Readiness Level
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
CRL	Customer Readiness Level
LLBM	Living Lab Business Model
BMC	Business Model Canvas
B2B	Business-to-Business
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PCP	Pre-commercial Procurement
TA	Transnational Access
CA	Contract Agreement
BA	Bilateral Agreement
OLLD	Open Living Lab Days
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
KVIs	Key Value Indicators

Executive summary

Although Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have been shown to be a “key” to the integration of research and innovation processes in real-life settings, they still fail to provide and function according to unified and harmonized processes that are easily accessible and exploitable by academic and industry researchers. Towards this end, VITALISE aims to create the first Harmonization guidelines for Living Labs that will facilitate the access of researchers to the provided infrastructures.

This document presents the work performed for the Harmonization of the way Living Labs work for the fifth semester of VITALISE. Within the VITALISE project, various Harmonization activities were carried out with consortium partners and external stakeholders, to develop the Standard v0.5, building on the work done for the earlier versions of the Standard (v0.1, v0.2, v0.3 and v0.4). The first version of the Standard (v0.1) provided an overview of the state-of-the-art information about Living Labs in the VITALISE consortium and served as the foundational deliverable for the VITALISE Standards. The second version of the Standard (v0.2) introduced the process of developing and disseminating a Wiki page that incorporated v0.1 and updated the parts of the Standard that described the data and technologies used in living labs, using a Delphi study method, and collected the initial set of terms for the living lab lexicon. Additionally, during the second semester, the Harmonization Board was established, and a meeting with the Harmonization Body was held. In the third version of the Standard (v0.3) the device and technology taxonomy were updated through a Delphi study, several meetings were held for updating the services and procedures categorization, as well as several activities and sessions for collecting and achieving a preliminary agreement on living lab lexicon terms. Moreover, two templates were developed for the co-creation sessions conducted within the Joint Research Activities (JRAs) and also, during this third semester, the project held its second plenary meeting in Helsinki and the second Harmonization Body meeting. For the fourth version of the Standard (v0.4) a wide range of actions took place, including meetings and activities to update the Living Lab Lexicon terms and LL services, as well as define the Living Lab Innovation and Research phases. In addition, an analysis of the Open Call data was conducted related to stakeholders, services, and devices and some interviews with partners from the consortium and beyond. Furthermore, the finalization and approval of data and devices taxonomy from the Delphi study occurred, alongside the occurrence of the 3rd Harmonization Body meeting and one Harmonization Board meeting in January and February, respectively.

In this iteration for the current deliverable (Standard Version 0.5), a series of actions unfolded, commencing with meetings and activities aimed at refining and validating the Research and Innovation process and create a visual tool for the representation of the process. Progress was achieved in the validation of the general KPI table and the proposal of a preliminary set of questions for the self-assessment tool for living labs. Substantial advancements were made in the realm of methods and tools, including a preliminary categorization of the questionnaires and instruments utilized in the JRA pilots. Additionally, some ethics tools, along with templates for Data Controllers Agreements have been specified and presented in this deliverable. Lastly, the 4th and 5th Harmonization Body meetings were held, alongside a dedicated session in Open Living Lab Days 2023, focusing on the VITALISE Harmonization journey. The final Section of this document presents the Standard v0.5 that will be also published in the living lab harmonization wiki page.

1 Introduction

1.1 Description of WP2

Work Package 2 (WP2), “Common Standards, Procedures and Practices” is a core WP for the VITALISE project as it handles all the work and implementation for the Harmonization procedure that is being followed. Some of the main tasks are the establishment of the harmonization procedures within the consortium and beyond, the management and organization of the Harmonization procedure events (Harmonization Body and Board meetings) and the definition and update of the Standards and Key Performance Indicators by identifying and documenting the existing Living Lab processes, and the similarities and differences among the consortium’s Living Lab partners. The Standard Versions will be updated every six months until the end of VITALISE project.

VITALISE Harmonization Body is a wider community of stakeholders consisting of Living Lab researchers and practitioners, healthcare professionals, policy makers and professionals that are interested in research performed in Living Lab infrastructures. VITALISE Harmonization Board aims to coordinate the Harmonization procedures and practices and consists of representatives from each Living Lab in the consortium, independent representatives from the Health and Wellbeing domain as well as policy makers. Representatives of other Health and Wellbeing Living Labs are also encouraged to join. This board will take decisions regarding the Standard Versions.

1.2 Purpose of the document

This document aims to present all the data collection and analysis that has been done between M24-M30 of the VITALISE project regarding the Harmonization activities. Although the deliverable is entitled “Standard Version 5”, the authors of this document decided that the specific standard should be Version 0.5 as it does not yet include all the parts required to reach Version 1.0. This will be the final version of the Standard and it is going to be released by the end of the project on M36. This document does not include only the Standard Version 0.5 of the Living Labs services, methods and tools but a more elaborate version, that includes the presentation of data collection, activities and analysis in order to result in the next Standard Version.

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1** (this section) provides information regarding the VITALISE project, aspects related to it, and the purpose of the document.
- **Section 2** discusses the activities that were performed during the fifth semester of living lab harmonization framework towards the creation of Standard v0.5.
- **Section 3** presents a summary of the changes and new additions that were made to the current version of the standard.
- **Section 4** includes all the information that will constitute the Standard Version 0.5. This Section is a coherent version of the Standard and can be read as a standalone document.
- **Section 5** provides some concluding remarks on this deliverable.

2 Activities performed towards the next standard version

In this latest iteration (Standard Version 0.5), key Harmonization actions focused on refining and validating the Research process, exploring its integration with the Innovation process, and harmonizing the evaluation of living labs. In this context, noteworthy efforts were directed towards validating the general Key Performance Indicator (KPI) table and designing a self-assessment tool. Moreover, the current Standard version saw several activities dedicated to updating the methods and tools section, including an initial categorization of questionnaires and instruments used in the JRA pilots, along with the incorporation of ethics tools. Finally, during this iteration, the 4th and 5th Harmonization Body meetings took place, along with a dedicated session during Open Living Lab Days 2023 addressing the VITALISE Harmonization process. This section outlines the activities undertaken to achieve these objectives.

2.1 Living Lab Lexicon Creation

In this phase of our work, our primary emphasis was on enhancing the reporting and dissemination of the ongoing developments within the Living Lab Lexicon project. To achieve this, we submitted a Research in Progress Paper for presentation at the Open Living Lab Days 2023 conference. The paper, titled "Harmonizing the Living Lab Language: Towards a Living Lab Lexicon (LLL)" provided a comprehensive account of the intricate processes involved in constructing an accessible and dynamic Living Lab Lexicon. These processes encompassed term identification, the selection of definitions, and the rigorous validation through both internal and external consensus-building mechanisms. We are pleased to announce that our submission was met with approval, resulting in its acceptance for an oral presentation during the conference. During the event, we had the opportunity to share our findings and insights with the conference attendees, further contributing to the discourse and progress in the field of Living Lab research.

We are now in the process of populating the VITALISE wiki with the definitions and the concept map presented above. These constitute the Open Access Dynamic Living Lab Lexicon.

2.2 Filling the Living Lab Business model

"A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value" (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). LLBM part is grounded on Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach (Ibid.), which consists of the following nine different elements. (1) key activities, (2) key resources, (3) partner network, (4) value proposition, (5) customer segments, (6) channels, (7) customer relationships, (8) cost structure and (9) revenue streams. The living lab standard defines common attributes associated with each nine BMC elements.

The major update on the business model focuses on the value proposition element. Customer value proposition (CVP) defines how an organization aims to provide value to customers (Payne, Frow and Eggert, 2017). From a customer-enterprise perspective, "value proposition" is a dynamic statement that explains and summarizes the benefits that a service, product or solution offers to its customers or users and why this product or service should be chosen over other similar, competitive options (Johnson, Christensen and Kagermann, 2008; Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010).

In the previous standard version two main customer types were defined: 1) **End user**: A person who ultimately uses or is intended to ultimately use the product, service or process and 2) **Living lab research infrastructure end user**: A person or organization who purchases or uses living lab research infrastructure services to conduct a specific contract-based research and development activity (often focusing on specifically defined end user group). The follow-up proposed value proposition update defines value proposition for Living lab research infrastructure end user. As defined in the prior standard Living lab research infrastructure end users are **considered as Business-to-Business Customer (B2B)**, which can further be divided into quadruple helix stakeholder groups: 1) private, 2) public, 3) education/ research, and 4) civil society organizations and networks/cluster groups.

An expert opinion evaluation research method (Goodman, 1987, Sackman, 1975; Baker, Lovell and Harris, 2006) was applied and open-ended questions (Kvale, 1996; Rubin and Rubin, 2011) were used for collecting value proposition suggestions from VITALISE Harmonization Body members (N=22). The data collection took place during the VITALISE Harmonization Body meeting which was held virtually, on the 17th of January 2023. The participants were asked to report through the mentimeter platform their opinions regarding the value they consider that the Living Labs can actually offer. Participants provided anonymously their suggestions about the value that Living Labs provide to each of the following customer groups: 1) researchers, 2) policy makers and public authorities, and 3) SMEs/companies and 4) for different Technology Readiness Level phases (TRL 1-9) which were grouped in three different level groups (TRL 1-3, TRL 4-6, TRL 7-9). In total, 57 answers were collected regarding the value propositions for the researchers, 32 for the policy makers and public authorities and 46 for the SMEs/companies. Regarding value proposition related to TRLs, 26 answers were collected for TRL 1-3, 27 answers for TRL 4-6 and 21 answers for TRL7-9. In all 209 value proposition suggestions were provided.

A publication titled “Towards living lab value proposition: Living lab experts’ perceptions on living lab value” was accepted to OpenLivingLab Days 2023, which took place in 21-23 September 2023 in Barcelona, Spain. Publication was scored among the six top contributions and was presented in the conference top session. An extended version has also been submitted to the Special Issue of the Journal of Innovation Management on “Living Labs and Collaborative Innovation”. Table 1 summarises the key living lab value arguments as presented in the publications.

Table 1 Living lab value arguments and generalised benefits based on expert opinions

Living lab expert arguments	Benefits derived from literature relating arguments
Economic benefits	
Refers to gains that can be expressed in financial terms resulting from the Living Lab innovation process or the improvement of the developed solution.	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Living lab can provide funding (e.g., via open calls) 2. Support to gain investments 3. Faster development time 4. Fail fast 5. Risk reduction 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cost savings, 2. Reduced development costs, 3. Increased Efficiency, 4. Shorter time-to-market, 5. Funding
Improved innovation	
Refers to all the different aspects in which the developed solution, whether it be a product, service, process, decision, policy, etc., could be better than existing and competing solutions.	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Better solutions 2. Prioritization 3. State of the art / current status 4. Local and Internationalization market knowledge / marketing 5. Marketing support 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Better product design, 2. Improved quality, 3. Better problem solving, 4. Better decision making, 5. Competitive advantage, 6. Increased creativity and innovation, 7. Access to new markets
Validity and reliability	
Refers to the stability of findings and validity to the truthfulness of findings.	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Living labs have extensive methodological expertise 2. Real-life 3. Test, Validation / impact analysis (Iterative validation) 4. Proof of concept 5. Risk reduction 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enhanced ecological validity, 2. Improved external validity, 3. Better generalizability, 4. Increased validity, 5. Richer data, 6. Complementary insights
Benefits for the users and society	
Refers to the impact of Living Lab studies in these groups.	

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Verified user acceptance 2. Needs and wants 3. Identification and definition of relevant target groups for your study purposes 4. Needs and requirements 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enhanced User Experience 2. Improved User / customer Satisfaction 3. Enhanced Social and Environmental Impact
<p>Enhanced collaboration and networking possibilities</p> <p>Refers to more diverse and multidisciplinary collaborations and bringing together stakeholders from different industries and fields while fostering cross-sectoral and interdisciplinary collaboration and opening up new and sometimes unexplored opportunities for cooperation.</p>	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Providing access to user and engaging them across different innovation process phases 2. Networking and collaboration opportunities 3. Multi/Interdisciplinary 4. Innovation network orchestration 5. Panel management 6. Co-creation 7. Engagement / Involvement / feedback 8. Publications 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increased Opportunities for Collaboration 2. Improved Communication and Collaboration: 3. Enhanced Collaboration 4. Strengthened Partnerships and Networks 5. Increased Stakeholder Engagement and Ownership 6. Greater Access to Participants 7. Increased Efficiency 8. Improved Resource Allocation
<p>Safe environment for RDI</p> <p>Refers to the provision of the mechanisms for ensuring regulatory and legal compliance.</p>	
Ethics	Protecting Human Participants
Risk reduction	Upholding Public Trust
	Ensuring Fairness
	Promoting Integrity
	Preventing Research Misconduct
	Meeting Legal Requirements
	Regulatory Compliance
<p>Increased skills and capabilities</p> <p>Refers to a process that enhances the knowledge, skills, and abilities of individuals, organizations, or communities to understand the key principles of the Living Lab approach.</p>	
Capacity building	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Skills to do user centric innovations 2. Understanding agile/iterative/ innovation process 	

Value propositions were prioritized based on the number of responses for each of the seven main value argument elements while comparing possible differences among different customer groups and TRL levels. The most prominent value proposition element was “enhanced collaboration and networking possibilities”, which was closely followed by validity and reliability argument. Together these two covered over half of all the value proposal suggestions. When adding the third most popular argument – Improved innovation – the total coverage remains ca. 70 percent range. “Economic benefits” and “Benefits for the users and society” gained somewhat same attention and covered together about 20 percent. “Safe environment for RDI” and “Increased skills and capabilities” appeared to be more marginal values for living lab expert since together they cover less than 10 percent of the expert suggestions.

Additional analysis revealed that “economic benefits” are mainly highlighted for companies (41.7 % share) while “increased skills and capabilities” (41.7 %) and “collaboration and networking opportunities” (39.8 %) are emphasised for researchers. Safe environment for RDI (41.7 %) gain substantial popularity in TRL 4-6 group. For the remaining main elements, the popularity divided more evenly.

2.3 Activities towards definition of the Living Lab Research and Innovation Phases

In the pursuit of defining and validating the phases of Living Lab Research and Innovation, the participating VITALISE Living Labs (LLs) were reached out to for insights into the processes and services employed in their completed Transnational Access (TA) studies. To facilitate this, a Miro board was created and shared with the LLs, featuring dedicated Research and Innovation Map (Figure 1) for each completed TA. The LLs were requested to identify and pinpoint the key services and processes that played a pivotal role in the completion of each of the performed TA studies.

Figure 1 Living Lab Research and Innovation process Map (initial version)

In essence, several commonalities were observed among the services and procedures employed within and across the participating LLs during the execution of the initial TA studies, albeit with subtle variations.

Commencing with touchpoints, the LLs overwhelmingly identified the Research/Innovation need or idea and the learning interest as crucial factors in executing the TA studies, with all 8 and 7 out of 8 TAs respectively reflecting this emphasis. Additionally, there was a significant mention of the need for data (6 out of 8 TAs), contacts (5 out of 8 TAs), and equipment or facilities (4 out of 8 TAs). Notably, one LL highlighted the funding need for a specific TA study, initiating discussions on EU funding opportunities in the context of fostering ongoing collaborative research with the hosting LL.

Progressing to customer acquisition part, the processes of Intake and matching and Contract/consortium agreement emerged as fundamental, being integral to 7 out of 8 conducted TA studies. For intake and matching, most LLs stressed the importance of pre-visit teleconferences for identifying potential participants/stakeholders and planning research activities. Regarding Contract Agreement (CA), besides the VITALISE CA, some cases required a Bilateral Agreement (BA) between the hosting and visiting organizations to delineate additional details and access requirements. Capacity building and Offer preparation were also deemed essential for the majority of TA studies (6 out of 8 and 4 out of 8 TAs respectively), with one LL specifying Access to data and Equipment & rental facility as necessary for supporting a TA study.

Advancing to project planning, detailed project planning (7 out of 8 TAs) and research protocol definition (6 out of 8 TAs) were procedures followed in the majority of the TA studies, accompanied by the Ethical application preparation (5 out of 8 TAs) and the Ethics committees (4 out of 8 TAs) as well. Communication and online meetings played a crucial role in defining research activities, participants, and methodologies for these processes. Additionally, during 4 out of 8 TA studies, LLs indicated the need for Stakeholder analysis.

In the project implementation and dissemination phase, project management (6 out of 8 TAs), panel management (5 out of 8 TAs), and stakeholder engagement (6 out of 8 TAs) were highlighted as essential. Participant recruitment was considered necessary for 4 out of 8 TAs, with 2 of them requiring Ad hoc recruitment. Testing, validation, and impact assessment were undertaken in 4 out of 8 TA studies, while co-creation was referenced in 3 others. Data analysis, including data cleaning in one case, was conducted in half of the completed TAs. Finally, results reporting/publication writing was emphasized by LLs for the majority of TAs (6 out of 8), followed by the mention of Dissemination in 4 out of 8 TAs. Future collaboration and contribution to analysis/reporting were highlighted as intentions by the LLs, with a focus on joint publications and exploring avenues for disseminating study results.

The aforementioned input and remarks provided by the involved LLs have been consolidated and visually presented in the following table.

Table 2 Results from gathered from VITALISE Living Labs regarding the Research and Innovation process Map

	Touch points	Customer acquisition	Detailed project planning	Project implementation & dissemination
AUTH – ID9	-Need for contacts -Need for data -Learning interest -Research/ innovation need or idea	-Capacity building -Intake & matching -Contract/ consortium agreement	-Stakeholder analysis -Detailed project planning -Research protocol definition -Ethical application preparation -Ethics committees	-LL project mgmt. -Panel mgmt. -Stakeholder engagement -Participant recruitment -Co-creation -Data analysis -Results reporting/ publication writing -Dissemination
AUTH – ID28	-Need for contacts -Need for data -Learning interest -Research/ innovation need or idea	-Capacity building -Intake & matching -Contract/ consortium agreement	-Stakeholder analysis -Detailed project planning -Research protocol definition -Ethical application preparation -Ethics committees	-LL project mgmt. -Panel mgmt. -Stakeholder engagement -Participant recruitment -Co-creation -Results reporting/ publication writing -Dissemination
AUTH – ID34	-Need for contacts -Need for data -Learning interest -Need for equipment or facility -Research/ innovation need or idea	-Capacity building -Intake & matching -Contract/ consortium agreement	-Stakeholder analysis -Detailed project planning -Research protocol definition -Ethical application preparation	-LL project mgmt. -Panel mgmt. -Stakeholder engagement -Participant recruitment -Testing, validation, impact assessment

			-Ethics committees	-Results reporting/publication writing -Dissemination
LICALAB – ID20	-Need for contacts -Need for data -Learning interest -Need for equipment or facility -Research/innovation need or idea	-Capacity building -Intake & matching -Contract/consortium agreement	-Stakeholder analysis -Detailed project planning -Research protocol definition -Ethical application preparation	-LL project mgmt. -Panel mgmt. -Stakeholder engagement -Co-creation -Data analysis -Results reporting/publication writing
LICALAB – ID43	-Need for data -Need for equipment or facility -Research/innovation need or idea	-Access to data -Equipment & rental facility -Intake & matching -Offer preparation -Contract/consortium agreement	-Detailed project planning -Research protocol definition -Ethical application preparation -Ethics committees	-LL project mgmt. -Panel mgmt. -Stakeholder engagement -Testing, validation, impact assessment -Data cleaning -Data analysis -Results reporting/publication writing
INTRAS – ID13	-Need for contacts -Need for data -Learning interest -Need for equipment or facility -Research/innovation need or idea -Funding need	-Capacity building -Intake & matching -Offer preparation -Contract/consortium agreement	-Detailed project planning	-LL project mgmt. -Stakeholder engagement -Results reporting/publication writing
LAUREA – ID33	-Learning interest -Research/innovation need or idea	-Offer preparation		-Participant recruitment -Ad hoc recruitment -Testing, validation, impact assessment
AIT – ID24	-Learning interest -Research/innovation need or idea	-Capacity building -Intake & matching -Offer preparation -Contract/consortium agreement	-Detailed project planning -Research protocol definition	-Ad hoc recruitment -Testing, validation, impact assessment -Data analysis -Dissemination

2.4 Harmonization Board and Body meetings and consortium workshops

Throughout this current semester iteration, several harmonization procedure events were orchestrated within and beyond the consortium. The overarching objective was to establish a unified approach and comprehension of the ongoing status, as well as to delineate the forthcoming steps in the harmonization effort.

2.4.1 4th Harmonization Body meeting

The 4th Harmonization Body meeting took place during the face-to-face plenary meeting that was held in Vienna between the 6th and 7th of March. The main scope was to allow people to familiarise themselves with the newly created Research & Innovation Map (Figure 1). The participants were split in groups and were asked to identify any tools/materials/templates that should be included in the harmonization documentation (next standard version) in order to help execute each step/module in the map. They were also asked to identify any steps/modules that are considered missing within the Research and Innovation process. The results helped structure the upcoming activities for the 5th Harmonization Body meeting.

Figure 2 Snapshot from the 4th Harmonization Body Meeting

2.4.2 5th Harmonization Body meeting

The 5th Meeting of the Harmonization Body convened virtually on the Zoom platform, hosting 39 registered participants on September 15, 2023. The primary focus of this meeting centered on the upcoming stages of the harmonization process and the categorization of Living Lab services. Prior to the meeting, Living Labs were tasked to populate a Miro board with information on the processes and services utilized in completed Transnational Access (TA) studies (see Section 2.3).

Kicking off with a warm welcome and an introduction outlining the meeting's scope by the Project Coordinator, the session progressed to updates on Living Lab Standards.

Post-introduction, an engaging and interactive discussion unfolded, with participants providing feedback and suggestions for refining the presented services and connections that are depicted in the Research and Innovation Map (Figure 1). Notably, the discussion spotlighted instances where several Living Labs did not adhere to all the steps and processes outlined in the illustrated routes. Additionally, there was consensus on the need for more methodology options in certain cases, such as the "Project implementation and dissemination phase," beyond the existing trio of secondary research, co-creation, and testing, validation, and impact assessment.

The 5th Harmonization Body meeting concluded with a deliberation on the sustainability of the Harmonization Body itself, followed by closing remarks that encapsulated the key takeaways and considerations from the constructive dialogue.

Figure 3 Snapshot from the 5th Harmonization Body meeting

2.4.3 VITALISE Harmonization session in Open Living Lab days

During the Open Living Lab Days (OLLD) held at the World Trade Center in Barcelona from the 21st to the 23rd of September 2023, a dedicated VITALISE session, titled "Living Lab Harmonization: the journey towards a common language," was organized by ThessAHALL, Laurea University, and McGill-CRIR Living Labs. The primary objective of this session was to offer attendees a comprehensive understanding of the ongoing Living Lab Harmonization process, specifically focusing on the VITALISE initiative. This initiative aims to integrate Living Labs into the broader Research Infrastructure ecosystem, emphasizing their integral role as components of Research Infrastructures.

The session sparked a thoughtful and engaging discussion among participants, underscoring the significance of establishing a "standardized" Harmonization methodology. The focus was on processes, tools, and services used by Living Labs in the Health and Wellbeing domain, with an emphasis on the need to extend this knowledge to other sectors. The discussion delved into the reality of the harmonization cycle within the VITALISE project, shedding light on challenges faced and the imperative for ongoing progress and evolution, recognizing the iterative and dynamic nature of the process. The subsequent steps involve further testing of the outcomes among Living Labs, achieving consensus, and adopting a "standard" version endorsed by European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL). This collaborative approach aims to foster value, trust, and cooperation among all stakeholders involved.

The session also explored the need for a common language and understanding among Living Labs, referencing the VITALISE roadmap of the Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) creation. The discussion aimed to facilitate communication between stakeholders with diverse backgrounds, balancing "standard" definitions within the broader scope of Living Labs and domain-sensitive, person-sensitive communication that is adaptive to specific needs.

An essential component of the session involved presenting the progress made towards a first version of Living Lab Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and a harmonized self-assessment tool. The ensuing discussion focused on future applications and the importance of distinguishing between KPIs and Key Value Indicators (KVIs), particularly in terms of satisfaction.

The session also highlighted the work done within VITALISE concerning the Living Lab Research and Innovation process. Emphasizing its iterative and agile nature, aligning with the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) concept, the presentation described a user-centered innovation and design process.

The session concluded on a promising note, setting a pivotal goal to articulate clear and actionable objectives for a dedicated Working Group within ENoLL. This Working Group will play a crucial role in advancing Living Lab Harmonization efforts and collaboratively establishing a concrete roadmap for the future.

Figure 4 Snapshots from the Harmonization session during Open Living Lab Days 2023

2.5 Collection of methods and tools

This section includes a description of activities that took place in order to create tools that will support the ethical applications for Living Lab studies and a first categorization of the validated questionnaires and tools that are commonly used in Living Labs.

2.5.1 Protocol templates creation

Living Labs have emerged as powerful platforms for the co-creation, testing, and validation of novel technologies, products, and services. They encourage open collaboration among stakeholders, including researchers, industry partners, and end-users, resulting in solutions that align more closely with real-world needs. These real-world environments require users to actively participate in the development process, offer invaluable insights into the feasibility, usability, and impact of innovations. Living Labs are unique in their ability to blend research and practice, making them ideal for fostering innovation. Yet, this fusion of research and practice introduces complex ethical considerations that demand careful considerations, standardization, and proactive management. These considerations encompass a wide spectrum, ranging from data privacy and informed consent to transparency and equitable access. A valuable and necessary tool that allows performing innovative endeavours while ensuring ethical responsibility in Living Labs is the study protocol.

Study protocols serve as the foundational blueprint for any research activity, outlining the objectives, methodologies, and ethical guidelines that researchers must adhere to. For these reasons, the study protocol is a requirement for ethics application, for it will inform the relevant ethics committee in their decision to greenlight the study and it will hold accountable the researcher to safeguard and uphold

the ethical principles of research. In addition, the study protocol is a tool in the hands of Living Labs to achieve research outcomes of the highest quality by promoting and ensuring:

- **Ethical Integrity:** Living Labs involve the active participation of individuals and communities, often as co-creators or testers of innovations. Ensuring that their rights and well-being are respected necessitates the adherence to ethical standards. Study protocols are the means by which these standards are articulated and upheld, safeguarding participants' rights, agency and interests.
- **Transparency:** Transparent research practices are essential to foster trust among all stakeholders. Study protocols detail how data will be collected, used, and shared, providing transparency to the research process. This transparency builds trust with end-users, industry partners, and regulatory bodies.
- **Consistency, Replicability and Quality assurance:** By standardizing research methodologies and procedures, study protocols enable the consistent execution of experiments and studies across different Living Labs. This consistency not only enhances the validity of findings but also facilitates cross-Lab comparisons and replicability of results, while ensuring high research quality and promoting a culture of excellence.
- **Regulatory Compliance:** Study protocols guide researchers and stakeholders navigate the complex landscape of local, national, and international regulatory requirements, ensuring that ethical principles are upheld.
- **Risk Mitigation:** Study protocols, especially for interventional studies, require from the researcher to balance the potential risks to the expected benefits from performing the study. Should risks are identified the researcher is required to take measures and outline strategies for their mitigation, minimizing potential harm to participants and the wider community.
- **Resource Allocation:** Living Labs often involve significant resources, including financial, human, and technological assets. Study protocols provide a structured approach to resource allocation, helping ensure that investments are well-placed and research goals are met efficiently.

For all the above VITALISE has created two study protocol templates to promote research activities and help navigate the regulatory requirements. The first protocol template is tailored for the core activity of Living Labs, that is the co-creation process where stakeholders are engaged to provide feedback and requirements. The second protocol template is more generic and aimed for interventional studies, which usually follow the co-creation activities, where the co-created research item is tested in real-life environments. The rationale behind creating two protocol templates is to provide agility and options to the potential Living Lab researchers on their most common research activities.

The protocol templates have arisen as an update from the initial templates that were used in JRAs, based on the integration of feedback from VITALISE Living Labs. Both protocol templates were utilized during the Transnational Access activities of VITALISE and subsequently were refined according to comments received by the ethics committees to which they were submitted.

2.5.2 Model contract for data sharing

The Data Transfer Agreement (DTA)/Joint-Controller Agreement (JCA) is a versatile and essential tool to address the pressing need for scientific collaboration. Even though, data transfer agreements were in place between entities, the DTA/JCA came into prominence when GDPR came into force, by setting the framework, requirements and obligations for personal data transfers described in Article 45 of GDPR. At its core, a DTA/JCA is a contract that outlines the roles and responsibilities of each partner under which personal data can be shared, transferred, and processed. While its significance extends across various domains, including business, research, healthcare, and e-commerce, the following factors underscore the critical importance of a standardized DTA template:

- **Data Privacy Compliance:** Organizations must demonstrate compliance when transferring personal data. DTA/JCAs provide a standardized way to meet the legal obligations derived

from the GDPR and other similar legislation, such as the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA).

- **Data Subject Rights:** DTA/JCAs must include provisions related to data subject rights, ensuring that individuals' rights related to their personal data are respected and actionable.
- **Accountability, Trust and Transparency:** Personal data transfer involves trust between parties – the data provider and the recipient. A well-structured DTA/JCA fosters transparency by clearly defining the party roles, the scope of data sharing, the purposes for data processing, and the security measures in place.
- **Risk Mitigation:** Data breaches and mishandling can result in financial, reputational, and legal repercussions. DTA/JCAs help identify potential risks and outline security measures to mitigate them, especially when they include Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) clauses.

VITALISE identified that DTA/JCAs can streamline the data transfer process, saving time and resources for Living Labs and cooperating organisations. By providing a standardized template for data transfer contracts, the negotiations are expected to be simplified and the need for bespoke agreements for each data transfer be reduced.

The Living DTA/JCA is created as a template and can be adapted to different study protocols. The current version is validated by VITALISE Living Lab partners for data exchanges that are taking place during the JRAs.

2.5.3 Living Lab methods and tools

The VITALISE Harmonization framework endeavors to integrate various pre-existing initiatives aimed at harmonizing tools and methodologies within the domain of Living Labs. This initiative seeks to expand the scope of harmonization and foster greater participation in the process, ultimately striving for a more comprehensive and universally embraced approach. In pursuit of this goal, we have initiated dialogues with the Unalab H2020 project with the intent of assimilating the UnaLab co-creation tools (accessible at <https://unalab.enoll.org/>) into the Living Lab Harmonization framework.

In the forthcoming months, we will dedicate our efforts to a thorough exploration of how this integration can be seamlessly and effectively executed. Our aim is to synergize these valuable resources, leveraging the strengths of both initiatives to create a harmonization framework that is not only holistic but also highly efficient and widely adopted within the Living Lab community.

2.5.4 Questionnaires and instruments from the JRAs

Working towards a first categorization of the tools and questionnaires employed during Joint Research Activities (JRAs), all participating Living Labs were assigned to complete an Excel spreadsheet on Teams. Each LL was required to list the questionnaires and instruments intended for use in their respective pilots within the JRAs. Following this data collection, the inputs were systematically organized into four primary axes, guided by their purpose and the aspects they measure.

These four fundamental categories are as follows:

1. Health Status & Wellbeing
2. Cognitive Status
3. Physical Activity/Mobility
4. Usability & User Experience Measures

For every questionnaire and tool falling under these axes, the variable measured was identified precisely. The culmination of this effort is encapsulated in the corresponding Part 7C of the Standard, summarizing the tools and the variables measured within each of the aforementioned categories.

2.6 Harmonizing the evaluation of living labs

The harmonization of evaluating living labs continued this year, based on the VITALISE-paper 'Harmonizing the evaluation of living labs: a standardized evaluation framework' (Vervoort, K. et al.,

2022) and taking further steps after the described work in Deliverable 4.5 - Living Lab Guidelines (first version). As a quick recap we sketch the steps taken within the multi-method approach of Deliverable 4.5 here below once again:

1. An extensive literature review (175 papers) to collect input around the evaluation and maturity of living labs
2. A desktop review concerning definitions and KPIs from current and past projects from ENoLL and external organizations/projects assessing living labs (20 frameworks)
3. An online validation survey (n=24) to define valid criteria descriptions
4. Analysis and clustering of all inputs from the previous steps
5. Definition of the criteria descriptions
6. Definition of a general KPI table for living labs based on the chapters and criteria of the published paper mentioned here above

Based on this work done earlier, from May 2023 onwards we continued with following steps. These steps will be further explained in detail within this deliverable.

7. Validation of the general KPI table for living labs by multiple relevant stakeholder groups (n=51)
8. Analysis of given comments/feedback
9. Iteration of the general KPI table for living labs
10. Proposal of a first set of scoring tables for each criterion
11. Proposal of a first set of questions for the self-assessment tool for living labs

Finally, we'll continue our work from October 2023 onwards by:

12. Validation of the iterate general KPI table by multiple relevant stakeholder groups
13. Evaluation and iteration of the proposed scoring tables
14. Validation of the proposed questions for the self-assessment tool for living labs
15. Integration of the necessary terms into the living lab lexicon
16. Definition of the full assessment process of living labs (quantitative and qualitative steps of the process)
17. Technical implementation of the self-assessment tool for living labs

2.6.1 Validation of the general KPI table

The KPI table as proposed in Deliverable 4.5 (see Annex 1) was validated by 6 different groups of stakeholders, all related to the evaluation and maturity of living labs:

- VITALISE pilot group, existing out of living lab practitioners from the project, ENoLL and Forum LLSA
- Members of the ENoLL office, interacting with living labs on a daily basis within different projects and within the ENoLL network
- Members of the ENoLL Labelling and certification task force, responsible for the design and execution of accepting and benchmarking ENoLL living lab members
- Members of the ENoLL executive board, expert living lab practitioners driving the objectives of the ENoLL network
- Members of the Forum LLSA, expert living lab practitioners from the health sector in France
- Academic living lab experts, identified within the literature review executed

At the end of June 2023 an interactive online session with the pilot group was organized (n=23) in which a validation exercise was introduced via MIRO. At the beginning of July, the same validation exercise was introduced to the members of the ENoLL office (n=22) and the ENoLL labelling and certification task force (n=4) during a meeting. Next to this, invitations were sent via email to participate in the validation exercise to members of the ENoLL executive board (n=15) and members of the Forum LLSA (n=23). Finally, an invitation was sent to academic living lab experts (n=10), identified within the literature review to participate also in the validation exercise.

In total 51 persons participated in the validation exercise:

- VITALISE pilot group (n=23)
- Members of the ENoLL office (n=10)
- Members of the ENoLL Labelling and certification task force (n=1)
- Members of the ENoLL executive board (n=9)
- Members of the Forum LLSA (n=5)
- Academic living lab experts (n=3)

All participants answered two questions via MIRO (Figure 5):

1. Is the KPI clear/unclear (green/red post-it)?
2. Which KPI is hard to measure according to your experience (orange post-it)?

All participants could add comments on the post-it's to provide more in-depth feedback.

2.6.2 Analysis of given comments/feedback

All the comments and votes from the 51 people participating in the validation exercise were compiled in an overview document with all-given comments and an analysis of the votes took place in a merged voting excel overview. Based on the excel overview an analysis took place of clear/unclear KPI's and KPI's hard to be measured for defining which KPI's need to be iterated.

To do so, following criteria were considered:

- every KPI with a score <80% of clarity was reinvestigated to iterate the wordings
- every KPI with a score >80% of clarity was considered ready for implementation without iteration in the wording of it
- every KPI with a score >25% of hardness to measure was reinvestigated to better scope the measurement

This performed analysis showed:

- 22 KPI's which needed to be reinvestigated concerning their clarity and iterate the wordings of them
- 18 KPI's concerning their hardness to measure, needing to be reinvestigated to better scope their measurement
- 15 KPI's of the categories here above were overlapping.
- 28 KPI's can be considered ready for implementation without iteration in the wording of it

After this, the comments document was used to support this analysis and to suggest iterated versions of the KPIs (Figure 6). Finally, to safeguard the biggest level of co-creation all valuable comments for clarification were considered, even if KPIs were perceived as ready for implementation.

Strategy	Clear (n=23)				Unclear (n=16)				Hard to measure (n=12)				Total (n=51)		Total votes								
	Clarity	Hard	Measure	Other	Clarity	Hard	Measure	Other	Clarity	Hard	Measure	Other	Clarity	Other									
Knowledge	9	0	5	1	1	3	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	6	4	0	0	23	9	9	71,88	25,95	
Business Model	7	2	4	4	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	0	8	2	0	4	3	0	31	1	2	72,86	2,98
Culture & Collaboration	7	0	2	4	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	9	1	0	6	0	0	29	1	2	71,38	3,13
Operations	6	2	4	4	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	10	0	0	3	0	3	22	3	8	73,33	9,89
Equipment & Infrastructure	6	1	2	3	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	9	1	1	4	0	0	36	1	1	75,00	17,86
Openness	6	1	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	1	0	7	1	2	1	0	6	18	3	8	69,23	10,34
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	3	1	1	4	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	5	3	2	5	0	1	20	4	4	70,00	14,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	3	2	2	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	6	3	1	5	0	0	20	5	3	69,00	17,86
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	4	0	3	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	5	2	3	0	2	5	24	2	3	66,67	6,49
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	3	0	4	0	0	1	0	0	2	1	0	4	5	1	7	0	0	25	9	1	68,00	14,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	3	3	1	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	5	3	3	3	0	4	21	2	10	67,19	6,49
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	4	0	3	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	5	2	3	0	2	5	17	1	6	64,71	7,86
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	4	0	2	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	9	1	4	3	0	9	9	19	5	64,29	17,86
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	1	0	3	0	0	3	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	5	5	3	1	7	6	12	64,29	25,95
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	2	0	3	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	4	0	6	4	1	0	21	4	7	71,00	12,00
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	2	0	3	1	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	5	0	5	4	1	0	22	4	5	68,18	12,00
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	1	0	2	1	0	1	0	0	2	1	0	0	9	1	1	3	2	13	15	3	69,23	14,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	2	3	3	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	3	7	0	0	1	5	9	18	9	60,00	20,00
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	4	3	2	0	1	1	0	0	2	1	0	2	2	6	2	1	3	12	8	13	59,09	20,00
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	1	1	4	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	28	2	2	71,43	6,25
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	1	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	5	0	1	26	2	1	69,23	6,80
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	1	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	28	2	0	71,43	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0	68,97	4,29
Operational partnerships, projects & processes	2	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	10	0	0	6	0	0	29	0	0		

3 Updates on the Standard

This Section summarizes the updates that were made in the corresponding Standard Version 0.5 compared to the previous one, Standard Version 0.4. As we are moving towards the end of the VITALISE project, all Standard parts are partially completed. Updates were included in Part 2, that also changed name from “Living Lab Business Model” to “Living Lab Governance and Business Model”. In this Section we described the value proposition for Living Labs, the current version of the Living Lab KPIs and a new section about the Living Lab Research and Innovation process as part of Living Lab Governance model. Furthermore, updates were applied to Part 7 Living Lab methods and tools with the addition of tools to support ethical submission applications and the first categorization of Living Lab validated questionnaires. For this Deliverable, the objectives that were defined along with the related project activities are presented in the following table.

Table 3 Objectives with the related project activities presentation

Standard and delivery date	Objective	Related project activities
Standard Version 5 – September 2023 [M30]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updates on Research process – connection with Innovation process phases • Updates on Methods and tools - ethics tools, questionnaires and instruments from the JRAs • Updates on Living Lab Business model - renamed as Living Lab Governance and Business Model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Call for external researchers - need for common procedures to be followed • Open Call for external researchers - need for common tools and instruments to be used • Need for harmonized evaluation of the LLs - description of value proposition for LLs and current version of the LL KPIs

3.1 Part 2 Living Lab Governance and Business Model

The updates introduced on this part, are coming from the results produced by the analysis of the VITALISE Harmonization Body members that resulted in a definition of the Living Lab Business Model Value proposition, as well as the Analysis of the Living Lab Key Performance Indicators that is part of the Living Lab Governance.

3.1.1 Living Lab Business Model

Grounded on our analysis, the following Living lab value proposition are formulated for companies, researchers and policy makers and public authorities:

Value proposition for companies:

Living Labs provide a compelling opportunity for companies to connect with users and actively involve them throughout various phases of the innovation process. This inclusive approach enables companies to effectively test, validate, and analyze the impact of their solutions iteratively. Moreover, by participating in Living Labs, companies gain access to enhanced networking and collaboration opportunities, fostering a dynamic ecosystem for innovation and growth.

Value proposition for policy makers and public authorities:

Living Labs present an effective platform for policy makers and public authorities to identify, engage, and involve users and diverse stakeholders throughout various phases of the innovation process. Through this collaborative approach, Living Labs facilitate the gathering of reliable feedback, needs, and requirements from the real end-users. Additionally, the

process allows for the verification of user acceptance, ensuring that policies and public initiatives are designed and implemented with a strong focus on meeting the genuine needs of the community they serve.

Value proposition for researchers:

Living Labs provide researchers with unparalleled networking and collaboration opportunities, fostering a rich environment for academic and practical exchange. Beyond this, Living Labs serve as a powerful platform for researchers to create and demonstrate proof of concept, enabling them to test and validate their research results iteratively. By aligning with the cutting edge of innovation, Living Labs offer researchers a unique space to refine and fine-tune their work, ensuring that it remains at the forefront of advancements in the field. Through these invaluable resources, researchers can drive their projects towards real-world impact and contribute meaningfully to societal progress.

3.1.2 Living Lab Governance – Key Performance Indicators

In August 2023 meetings were organized with WP2 partners from the VITALISE project, together with a meeting with the ENoLL Labelling and certification task force to iterate the general KPI table for living labs. As a result of this exercise, now 35 KPIs remain in the framework. Next to this the wording of most KPIs was adjusted to respond to the given comments during the validation exercise.

This iterated general KPI table for living labs, shown here below in Table 1 is to be validated by the same 6 groups of stakeholders in September 2023.

Table 4 Iterated general KPI table for living labs

Chapter	Criterion	KPI
Strategy	Governance	1. % of (active) involvement of a balanced and diverse group of stakeholders in the development of the vision & mission of the living lab (e.g., all Q4 represented is 100%)
		2. % of participation of a balanced and diverse group of stakeholders in the governance of the living lab (strategic & operational roles and decision-making processes)
		3. Presence of partner agreements/arrangements for co-innovation
		4. Completeness of a strategic roadmap for the living lab (SMART goals, responsibilities, and decision-making processes)
	Business Model	5. Completeness of the described business model approach (value propositions, problems & solutions, activities & resources, key stakeholders, customers, users, costs & revenues, metrics & impacts)
		6. Number of (different) services offered by the living lab (e.g., stakeholder engagement) covering (all) different phases of the innovation cycle

	Culture & Collaboration	7. Presence of internal & external business & client relation management process/strategy (including contracts)
		8. Frequency of internal communication & results sharing to keep partners informed & aligned
		9. Number of regional, national & international collaborations beyond the scope of an individual living lab project
Operations	Human Resources	10. % of Implementation of needed internal roles and responsibilities within the operational living lab team in a flexible way (are all roles sufficiently attributed depending on the size of the operational living lab team)
	Operations	11. Time spent within successfully completed projects and/or activities related to the living lab (how many weeks/months/years of experience does the living lab has in running projects and/or activities)
		12. Completeness & frequency of internal self-monitoring processes (how often is the living lab monitoring essential parts of their organization: strategic, financial, equipment & infrastructure, policy, project outcomes)
	Equipment & infrastructure	13. % accessibility in time to facilities (e.g., offices, co-creation spaces, testing facilities...)
		14. % accessibility in time to hard- & software (e.g., co-creation materials, computers, wearables, interaction software, polling/survey software...)
	Openness	Innovation partnerships, projects & processes
16. % of implementation of needed processes to safeguard an ethical approach (e.g., regulatory requirements, data protection needed, etc.)		
Ownership of results		17. % of implementation of needed rules & regulations regarding the use, sharing & licensing of data and IP of collaborative outcomes

		18. % of implementation of user agreements (data, IPR, rights, liabilities)
Users & reality	User centrality	19. % of diversity of stakeholders involved as end-users in living lab projects and/or activities
		20. Degree of influence end-users exerts on the different phases of the innovation cycle (from informing to empowerment)
	Lifecycle & real-life	21. Degree of involvement of end-users in the different phases of the innovation cycle e.g., problem space, solution space, implementation space...)
		22. Degree of use of real-life contexts of users in the different phases of the innovation cycle
	Tools & methods	23. Degree of appropriateness of tools & methods used for the different phases of the innovation cycle
		24. Frequency of external communication & results sharing to keep end-users and external stakeholders informed and engaged
Impact & value	Co-created values	25. % Satisfaction of users/stakeholders (from the whole value chain) concerning their involvement/influence on the innovation cycle
		26. Frequency of knowledge sharing (including results) with relevant (internal & external) stakeholders from the value chain
		27. Number of relevant (open) educational resources (including datasets, trainings) shared/provided for relevant stakeholders
		28. % Satisfaction of users/stakeholders concerning knowledge sharing & capacity building (learning materials & infrastructures)
	Impacts	29. Completeness & frequency of impact assessments (how often is the living lab monitoring different types of impacts they are generating: societal, environmental, economic, regulatory, academic)
Stability & harmonization	Stability	30. % Increase in number of relationships (with a reliable partner network and customers)
		31. Level of financial sustainability based on a balanced & diversified set of fundings

Harmonization & scale-up	(structural vs. project-based) & revenue streams
	32. Number of living lab value propositions, flexible to adapt to new circumstances
	33. % Increase in number of partners committed to scale up products/solutions/services developed by the living lab
	34. Number of products/solutions/services (able to be) scaled-up
	35. Number of participation in (cross-border/cross-sectoral) initiatives/projects based on harmonized living lab infrastructures, standards, skills, methods, tools processes or services

3.1.3 Living Lab Governance – Research and Innovation Process Map

Figure 7 presents updated version of the logical relationships between different living lab R&D services and key living lab asset repositories, presented in Figure 1. The updated version was created as a result of the feedback gathered during the 4th and 5th Harmonization Body meeting, as well as the OLLD23 session on Harmonization.

Figure 7 Current version of the Living Lab Research and Innovation process map

The current version includes following updates:

Touch points

- **Market entry/uptake customer:** Customer need added since in some cases customer could reach out to living labs with a market ready product to check the scalability in a specific region or wanting to perform the conditions of potential market entry/market uptake.

Customer acquisition

- **Accept terms and condition:** Before gaining access to data repositories, customer must agree on the terms and conditions for the data usage.
- **Access management:** There can be different access levels within the data repository which must be managed.
- **Link between offer preparation and stakeholder analysis:** During this phase living labs identify different potential target groups for the proposed project.
- **Subcontracting negotiation process:** Sometimes part of the project activities are conducted by subcontractors (e.g. transnational project where one living lab is acting as main contact point for the customer, while subcontractors are conducting project activities in their own location)

Detailed project planning

- **Desk/market research:** During this phase living labs preliminary identify different potential target groups for ideas/innovations/products/services to be able prepare offering. Links to stakeholder analysis and panel management were added as well.
- **IPR management:** Multistakeholder projects following co-creating principles can result complex IPR issues. Therefore, as a part of detailed project planning IPR management principles must be defined before starting the project.
- **Data governance policy:** It defines how data is 1) used and managed, 2) gives overview of all the roles and responsibilities related to data governance, and 3) other aspects of managing data assets, such as data quality, security, and access.
- **Data management plan:** Is formal document that outlines how data will be handled during and after a research project.
- **Research site permit:** Approval to conduct a specified research project over a specified and finite period in a giving site (e.g., in hospital ward or school).
- **Rejection link between ethical committee and ethic application preparation:** In many cases ethical committee will ask changes to submitted application.

Project implementation and dissemination

- **Consent form:** In most cases a project will need consent from study participants. A consent form signed by a study participant confirm that he or she agrees to the procedure and is aware of any risks that might be involved. The consent form provide evidence that the study participant has given his/her consent.
- **Quality management:** Quality management is one of project management tasks. It is overseeing all the planned/executed activities and tasks to maintain a desired level of excellence (e.g., determination of a quality policy, creating and implementing quality planning and assurance, and quality control and quality improvement).
- **Innovation process and services:** The original Innovation process and services was replaced by LL TRL process phases and LL service portfolio items. This highlight better that living lab service portfolio can cover all the TRL phases when needed and many of the services can be applied in multiple TRL phases.
- **Data anonymization and pseudonymization:** Data anonymization is the process of removing personally identifiable information from data sets, so that the people whom the data describe remain anonymous. Pseudonymization is a de-identification procedure where personally identifiable information fields within a data record are replaced by one or more artificial identifiers, or pseudonyms.

3.2 PART 7 Data Collection Approaches

In this version (v0.5) we have introduced two main changes in Part 7: 1) in Part 7A, under the Methods and Tools of the Standard, we've introduced Protocol Templates and a Model Contract for Data and 2) in Part 7C the categorization tables for questionnaires and instruments used in VITALISE JRAs.

3.2.1 PART 7A Methods and tools

We are delighted to announce the addition of two vital updates to this deliverable. First and foremost, we have introduced an extensive set of Protocol Templates within the Part 7A Methods and Tools of the Standard. These templates have been thoughtfully designed to cater to the unique requirements of a variety of study protocols. Additionally, to address the inherent diversity of study protocols and their associated data transfers, we have now included a Model Contract for Data Sharing, also within Part 7A Methods and Tools of the Standard. This model contract establishes a standardized framework, providing a robust foundation that can be customized to suit the distinct needs of different research projects, promoting efficient and secure data sharing practices.

3.2.2 PART 7C. Validated questionnaires and instrument

In Part 7A of Section 4 within the Standard version of this deliverable, we have introduced the tables that present the current categorization of Questionnaires and instruments from the JRAs, to provide a comprehensive overview of all the instruments and questionnaires utilized throughout the VITALISE JRAs, along with the measured variables.

4 Standard Version 0.4

This Section will be the fourth (v0.4) public version of Living Labs Standard. This Standard is considered Version 0.4 as there are still sections that are not defined and have not undergone a full cycle of Harmonization. As v1.0 we are considering the first version that will contain information for all available sections and will be delivered by the end of the project, on M36. This Section is structured in such a way so that it can be separated from the rest of the deliverable and published in the VITALISE wiki page as a standalone document.

4.1 Introduction

The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) – an international non-profit association promoting and enhancing user-driven innovation ecosystem defines living lab is *“a user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings”* (<https://enoll.org/about-us/>).

This wiki serves as an open space for the public review of the harmonization version and encourages open discussion about the various items that are presented. The information presented in this wiki will be updated every six months and published after approval from the governance Board and Body of the Harmonization process. In each section you can find when and by which each version is approved (e.g., “Approved by the VITALISE H2020 Living Labs' consensus report on XX/XX/XXXX”.)

The VITALISE Harmonization process is governed by two main groups, the VITALISE Harmonization Body and the VITALISE Harmonization Board. By VITALISE Harmonization Body we refer to a wider community of stakeholders consisting of Living Lab researchers and practitioners, healthcare professionals, policy makers and professionals that are interested in research performed in Living Lab infrastructures. VITALISE Harmonization Board aims to co-ordinate the Harmonization procedures and practices and is consisted of representatives of each Living Lab in the consortium as well as independent representatives from the Health and Wellbeing domain as well as policy makers. Representatives of other Health and Wellbeing Living Labs are also encouraged to join. This board will take decisions regarding the Standard Versions.

The aim of this Living Lab standard is to guide Living Lab operators and researchers to execute, develop and maintain a harmonized framework for systematic Living Lab practices. It is not a rigid and strict representation of what Living Labs are doing but it rather be used as guidelines towards the identification of common approaches. Living Labs are structures that encourage serendipity in the way that they are working and should be handled as such. The standard versions concern mainly the LLs but they also borrow knowledge, expertise and experience from various other domains, like open science, citizen science, open innovation, innovation management, responsible research and innovation etc. on a sharing basis. Within this framework, there are several tools and methodologies exploited in LLs which could also be applied in several other research contexts.

By Establishing Living Lab management system, the Living Labs will:

1. Promote the expansion and growth of Living Lab movement beyond current actors and customers,
2. Stimulate cross-organization and transnational research collaboration,
3. Enable data sharing and comparison of the research results,
4. Increase research quality, and
5. Define a common terminology and language among researchers and practitioners.

The Figure 4 defines the conceptual overview of the living lab management system presented in this standard document.

Figure 8: The key elements and conceptual overview of the living lab management system

The following key elements will concern the Living Lab community and will be further assessed in the next Standard Version.

1. Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) – terms and definitions: LLL introduces, lists and shortly defines a comprehensive catalogue of terms associated and included in different parts of the living lab standard (i.e., 2 to 9). The LLL is grounded on Wikipedia type of user interface, where definitions including overlapping terminology, will enable quick jumping between different descriptions and to in-depth descriptions in other standard sections. LLL will help to discuss living lab related issues among the different stakeholder, who currently are using varying terminology.

2. Living Lab Governance and Business Model: This Living Lab Harmonization Section consists of two parts: The Living Lab Business Model (LLBM) and the Living Lab Governance Model.

- “A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value” (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). LLBM part is grounded on Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach (Ibid.), which consists of the following nine different elements. (1) key activities, (2) key resources, (3) partner network, (4) value proposition, (5) customer segments, (6) channels, (7) customer relationships, (8) cost structure and (9) revenue streams. The purpose of the LLBM part is to identify different attributes associated with each nine BMC element. Having a unified way to describe LLBM enables quantitative business model comparison between different living labs as well as open ups possibilities to track changes in business model strategies.

- A governance model for Living Labs is a framework or set of principles that guide how a Living Lab operates, makes decisions, and manages its activities. It defines the rules, roles, responsibilities, and processes that ensure effective and efficient functioning of the Living Lab. The Living Lab Governance model of this Standard is underpinned by the identified Key Performance Indicators of Living Labs that cover all the aspects of Living Lab activities and functioning in a comprehensive framework.

3. Research process: The part ‘Living Lab research process’ focuses on defining the key steps to execute and define a living lab research methodology. The part is comprised of (1) a common template to define research protocol, (2) ethical and data management plans, (3) participant recruitment procedures, (4) infrastructure selection procedure, (5) data collection procedures, (6) data analysis and comparison practices and (7) fair data practices for opening data. Each phase consists of aim, outcome and maturity level description. Furthermore, research process phases are

interlinked with other living lab standard parts in order to identify which other items are relevant for each research process phase. Having a standard way to describe living lab research design helps developing a unified research methodology, which enables a robust results comparison across different studies, increasing the research quality.

4. Innovation process: Living Lab innovation process part focuses on defining in an unambiguous way, the different innovation management process phases which are or can be covered during the living lab data collection phase. This part defines an iterative and agile user-centered innovation and design process and align the phases with Technology Readiness Level (TRL) concept. TRL is widely adopted concept to describe developed solution maturity level. Respectively to research process, different innovation process phases are interlinked with other Living Lab standard parts in order to identify which of the other items are relevant for each process phase.

5. R&D services: R&D services refer to a group of common R&D services, which a Living Lab can offer to its' customers during the different Living Lab R&D process phases. Each service combines one or more data collection approaches or other activities or parts of the Living Lab standard, needed to accomplish living lab R&D project as whole or part of it. Each service description defines the type of service and additional details related to service delivery such as technical and functional quality. In the long run, the aim is to define the Minimum Acceptable Service Level for each service type in order ensure service quality across the different Living Labs.

6. Living lab Research Infrastructure (RI): This part provides a classification schema and definitions for different types of Living Lab infrastructures. In regulation No 1291/2013, European Union Parliament and Council of the European Union (2013) defines RIs as “facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields”. The definitions and descriptions for (1) single-sited, (2) distributed, (3) virtual and (4) mobile living lab facilities are provided.

7. Data collection approaches. Data collection approaches consist of the following three sub-parts: (1) methods and tools, (2) devices and technologies and (3) validated questionnaires and instruments. This part provides a collection of practical data collection approaches, which can be combined in multiple variations when defining a living lab project research methodology.

7A Methods and tools part identifies and describes the different types of specific research methods, tools, and practices, which can be used for data collection during a living lab project. Among these are e.g., interviews, workshops and surveys. In the future, the standard will be used for sharing the best practices and defining the appropriate ways to utilize the particular method in different living research contexts.

7B Devices and technologies defines a commonly used technological solutions to collect and analyse living lab research data. Correspondingly to 7A methods and devices, the standard will be used for sharing the best practices and defining the appropriate ways to utilize the particular technology in a research setting.

7C. Validated questionnaires and instrument consists of a numerous scientifically validated surveys, scales, interventions or similar, known to be reliable measure-certain phenomenon. The Standard will especially promote questionnaires and instruments which are multilingual and freely available. If multiple instruments are available to measure same phenomenon, standard will make recommendation to make selections.

To conclude, it is important to clarify that the above-described conceptual overview and the included key elements of the living lab management system are preliminary concepts. Therefore, the names, details and concept itself can be changed in the following versions.

4.2 Scope of this document

This is the fifth draft version of the Health and Wellbeing Living Labs Standard (Version 0.5). The structure and content of this document will be continuously improved, and a new version will be released every 6 months. The information presented is a result of an analysis performed in the VITALISE project and more details about the analysis can be found in the Deliverables of the project.

The Parts that are not presented here are the ones that have not yet undergone a full circle of Harmonization. The rest of the document presents:

- **PART 1 Living Lab Lexicon (LLL):** Collection of terms that are widely used in Living Lab performed activities.
- **PART 2. Living lab governance and business model:** The identified value proposition, the Living Lab KPIs and the Research and Innovation process map.
- **PART 3. Research process:** presenting the Living Lab research phases.
- **PART 4. Innovation process:** presenting the Living Lab Innovation phases.
- **PART 5. R&D Services:** A list of R&D services provided by Health and Wellbeing Living Labs.
- **PART 6. Living lab research infrastructure:** a first categorization of existing Living Lab infrastructures.
- **PART 7A. Methods and tools:** In this standard version we included the identified tools that support ethics applications.
- **PART 7B. Devices and technologies:** In this standard version identified devices and technologies are presented as a part of R&D service descriptions.
- **PART 7C. Validated questionnaires and instruments** contains a first categorization of the questionnaires and instruments that are used in Living Labs for performing research studies.

4.3 PART 1. Living Lab Lexicon (LLL)

It is the case clear that many stakeholders in the Living Lab ecosystem do not always use the same 'language' and the words used may allude to different concepts. This can sometimes lead to confusion and misunderstandings and can become even more apparent when talking to different 'players' across the Living Lab communities. VITALISE is in the process of creating a Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) with the aim to establish a repository where Living Lab key terms and definition(s) can be found and shared with the Living Lab community and beyond. The overall vision is to facilitate and increase understanding and communication between the different 'players' within the Living Lab communities and all those who come in contact with Living Labs.

In doing so, we are mindful of the fact that some words/terms can have different meanings depending on the context of use (same term/word but with more than one meaning). We also note that different groups of users may opt for different words to represent the same concept (different word/term but with the same or very similar meaning). To ensure that the word/term definitions found in the LLL reflect the perspectives of these main groups of potential users (Academia, Industry, Government, Citizens), we decided that it is important to include words/terms from the Innovation process and the Research process. We thus strive to ensure that the definitions included in the Living Lab Lexicon will reflect the diversity of context and use of the various potential users.

Using a rigorous term identification process, coupled with a verification of definitions through iterative co-creation sessions we have defined the first 30 LL terms and created a concept map that includes a subset of them.

Below we present the first LL concept map that integrates various definitions and their interlinks.

Figure 9 Living Lab concept map

We are now in the process of populating the VITALISE wiki with the definitions and the concept map presented above. These constitute the Open Access Dynamic Living Lab Lexicon.

4.4 PART 2. Living Lab Business and Governance Model

“A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value” (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). LLBM part is grounded on Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach (Ibid.), which consists of the following nine different elements. (1) key activities, (2) key resources, (3) partner network, (4) value proposition, (5) customer segments, (6) channels, (7) customer relationships, (8) cost structure and (9) revenue streams. The living lab standard defines common attributes associated with each nine BMC element.

This standard version focuses on defining customer segments in Health and Wellbeing Living Labs.

4.4.1 Customer segments in Health and Wellbeing Living Labs

End user: A person who ultimately uses or is intended to ultimately use the product, service or process. In living lab projects, the end user is defined as a primary study participant who voluntarily participates in research after giving informed consent to be the subject of the research.

Living lab research infrastructure end user: A person or organization who purchases or uses living lab research infrastructure services to conduct a specific contract-based research and development activity (often focusing on specifically defined end user group). Living lab research infrastructure end user can also be study participant (a.k.a. end user), if living project is focusing on developing living lab services and infrastructure.

End users can be classified as non-professional and professional groups. Typical non-professional and professional end-user groups in health and wellbeing includes the following:

- **Non-professional end users:**
 - **Consumers:** Those who buy goods or services for their own use.
 - **Public health and social service clients:** Those who use public services.
- **Professional end users**

- **Health professionals and managers:** A person providing health care treatment and advice based on formal training and experience. Also known as healthcare professional or healthcare worker.
- **Social care workers and managers:** Those providing the practical support to help people cope with the day-to-day business of living based on formal training and experience.
- **Policy and decisions makers:** Those responsible for making policies and decisions at local, regional, national or international level.

Business-to-Business Customer (B2B): B2B-customer is an organization that purchases living lab services from a living lab. B2B-customers can be classified to private, public, education/research, civil society organizations and networks/cluster groups as follows:

- **Private sector organizations:** (business developers and researchers)
 - Tangible equipment and device manufactures
 - Health and social service providers
 - e-health, IT system and digital technology providers
 - Wellbeing and wellness service providers
 - Pharmaceutical companies
- **Public sector organizations:**
 - **Local level:** Municipals, cities and other local level public organizations providing e.g., health and social services such as primary health care.
 - **Regional level:** e.g., regional hospitals providing secondary and tertiary care, councils, parliaments, and governments as well as other administrative organizations operating at regional level.
 - **National level:** Government agencies, departments or temporary pointed working groups responsible for the specific functions such as health and social services.
 - **International level:** European commission departments and agencies as well as other organizations operating at international and transnational level.
 - **Public funder:** Government or other European, national, regional or local public institutions who is providing public funding for a specific living lab living lab research project via call for application process.
- **Education and research organizations:**
 - **Higher education institutes:** Universities and Universities of Applied Sciences
 - **Other educational institutes** covering early childhood, primary, secondary and tertiary education.
 - **Public research institutions/organizations** such as technical research centers and government laboratories.
 - **Private research organizations** such as technology and innovation centers
- **Civil society organizations:**
 - Non-governmental organizations (NGO) and nonprofit entities operating at international, national, regional or local level.
- **Networks and clusters:**
 - Company cluster organizations and company networks
 - International, national, regional and local networks

Typical approaches to define non-professional end users (a.k.a. study participants) in health and wellbeing living lab projects are presented in Table 9.

Table 5 Classification approaches of non-professional end users commonly acting as a primary study participant in a health and wellbeing living lab research project

Age groups			
Specific age range			
Adolescents	Adults	Older Adults	General Population

Adolescents Health status (disease, disorder or disability)

Healthy			
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Adults Health status (disease, disorder or disability)			
Healthy	Schizophrenia	Multiple-Sclerosis	Parkinson Disease
Post-Stroke Patients with Moving or Linguistic Disability	Mild Cognitive Impairment	Sleep Disorders: e.g., Apnea, Hypopnea	With Disability
Healthy with Possible Chronic Conditions			

Older Adults Health status (disease, disorder or disability)			
Healthy	Parkinson Disease	Mild Cognitive Impairment	With Disability
Healthy with Possible Chronic Conditions			

General Population Health status (disease, disorder or disability)			
Healthy	Ipf Patients	Prostate Cancer	Down Syndrome
Chronical Diseases: e.g., Persons With Chronic Pulmonary (Copd)	Cardiological Or Other Conditions (Aphasia)	Breast Cancer Survivors	

Typical approaches to define professional end users in health and wellbeing living lab projects are presented in Table 10.

Table 6 Classification approaches of professional end users, students and organisations commonly acting as a primary study participant in a health and wellbeing living lab research project

Informal Caregivers			
Part of adults and citizens' group			

Health Care Professionals / Formal Caregivers			
Doctors	Social workers	Physiotherapists	Psychologists
Registered nurses	Practical nurses	Physicians	

Students			
Medical	Engineering	Computer Science	Pedagogues
English Literature	Nursing	Physiotherapy	Social Services.
Health Care Management			

Organizations			

Hospitals	Nursing homes	Care homes	Home care Organizations
Network organizations	Day care centers		

Living lab research infrastructure end users and B2B-customers in health and wellbeing living lab projects are presented in Table 11.

Table 7: Researchers' expertise

Researchers' expertise	Brief use case description
Citizen scientists, users as co-researchers	User empowerment, training, design, analysis and implementation of strategies and methodologies for user engagement and for raising awareness and generating citizen participation.
Computer, technology scientists	Developing systems/tools/ technologies, testing and evaluating an ICT tool, prototype and real-life testing, computer vision & AI, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality, Cybersecurity.
Data scientists	Collecting, analysing and interpreting digital data, such as data analytics in healthcare and digital patient recordings (how patient information recording process is managed and utilized during the intervention by using digital tools in simulated situations).
Rehabilitation (physical, cognitive) experts	Physiology, physiotherapy, occupational health research, rehabilitation and prevention. Cognitive diseases assistive technology, neuromuscular rehabilitation assistive technology.
UX research and assessment experts	Developing the process for user experience design (UXD, UED, or XD) supporting user behaviour through usability, usefulness, and desirability provided in the interaction with a product or service, addressing all aspects as perceived by users with a focus on the quality of the user experience. Studying and experimenting the best practices for UI/UX and evaluating user's experience in different situations and while using different tools.
Clinical expertise researchers	(Doctors, nurses, healthcare workers, specialists, physiotherapists etc.), conducting research of healthcare services and practices, research on symptomatology or epidemiology of a disease, analysis of clinical effects of research performed in the study, e.g., via real life testing.
Policymakers	Studying the impact of new service models or new collaboration models in healthcare, designing or improving policies, gathering requirements for

	improving health and wellbeing of citizens, co-creation of research methodologies for policy making.
Biomedical researchers	Studying biochemical and physiological functions, investigating how the human body works with the aim of finding new ways to improve health. Biomedical engineering knowledge (Home hospitalization, Transitional Care, Multifunctional interaction), as well as digital biomarkers analysis (e.g., for cognitive state).
Business developers	Studying the product-market fit, matching a solution with a societal need, learning about the user acceptance of products and services, as well as about potential products to develop, willingness to pay, business model and ideal route to market.
Innovation and design management researchers	Ecosystem and innovation management research, social network analysis. Evaluating how health and wellbeing ecosystem operates between different actors at local, regional, national and international level, including also scaling and commercialization.
Accessibility design experts	Validating accessible architectonics and escape route models with VR experiment and real-life simulations.
Ergonomics and safety experts	Implementation and validation of ergonomic technologies/services to support workers and system performance, promoting ergonomics in working environments, improving both health/well-being and productivity, while avoiding occupational hazards.
Organizational studies experts	Co-creation, experimentation, organizational research, experts by experience / peer support included. Evaluation how multistakeholder collaboration and co-creation is done and how effective it is. Evaluates experimentations and experimentation culture. How users are involved into these processes.
Neuroscientists	Focusing on the brain and its impact on behaviour and cognitive functions (cognitive neuroscience, EEG-based BMI research, protocol / paradigm testing, study framework evaluation).
Psychologists (clinical, social, developmental, neuro)	Studying the behaviour and the mental wellbeing of participants, conducting psychometrics evaluation and real-life setting experimentation/observation/real life testing.
Social workers/researchers	Conducting an investigation in accordance with the scientific methods and tools, studying the impact of new care models and/or care innovations on society, developing models for a caring and inclusive society.

Sport science experts	Experimenting novel training methods, and their effectiveness in various dimensions such as safety, engagement, and physical capabilities. Studying the impact of physical movements in various functions and wellbeing features.
Communication studies experts	Defining written, oral, visual and digital communication within a certain workplace. Evaluating (multi professional) healthcare team collaboration, communication and debriefing in various healthcare situations in simulated environments (especially in Simulation lab).
Performing arts experts	Creative health improvement (e.g., for cognitive decline) through music and dance (example: redesigning public spaces into healthy spaces: test and validate Smart methodologies, products and services through folk dance).
Pedagogues/educators	Evaluating different pedagogical approaches and their impact learning performance (especially in Simulation lab).
Applied economics experts	Evaluating cost and performance in different healthcare processes, situations and public health.

4.4.2 Living Lab Value proposition

Value proposition for companies:

Living Labs provide a compelling opportunity for companies to connect with users and actively involve them throughout various phases of the innovation process. This inclusive approach enables companies to effectively test, validate, and analyze the impact of their solutions iteratively. Moreover, by participating in Living Labs, companies gain access to enhanced networking and collaboration opportunities, fostering a dynamic ecosystem for innovation and growth.

Value proposition for policy makers and public authorities:

Living Labs present an effective platform for policy makers and public authorities to identify, engage, and involve users and diverse stakeholders throughout various phases of the innovation process. Through this collaborative approach, Living Labs facilitate the gathering of reliable feedback, needs, and requirements from the real end-users. Additionally, the process allows for the verification of user acceptance, ensuring that policies and public initiatives are designed and implemented with a strong focus on meeting the genuine needs of the community they serve.

Value proposition for researchers:

Living Labs provide researchers with unparalleled networking and collaboration opportunities, fostering a rich environment for academic and practical exchange. Beyond this, Living Labs serve as a powerful platform for researchers to create and demonstrate proof of concept, enabling them to test and validate their research results iteratively. By aligning with the cutting edge of innovation, Living Labs offer researchers a unique space to refine and fine-tune their work, ensuring that it remains at the forefront of advancements in the field. Through these invaluable resources, researchers can drive their projects towards real-world impact and contribute meaningfully to societal progress.

4.4.3 Living Lab Key Performance Indicators

Here we present the current version of the Living Lab Key Performance Indicators, derived by the activities described in section 2.6.

Table 8 Living Lab Key Performance Indicators

Chapter	Criterion	KPI
Strategy	Governance	1. % of (active) involvement of a balanced and diverse group of stakeholders in the development of the vision & mission of the living lab (e.g., all Q4 represented is 100%)
		2. % of participation of a balanced and diverse group of stakeholders in the governance of the living lab (strategic & operational roles and decision-making processes)
		3. Presence of partner agreements/arrangements for co-innovation
		4. Completeness of a strategic roadmap for the living lab (SMART goals, responsibilities, and decision-making processes)
	Business Model	5. Completeness of the described business model approach (value propositions, problems & solutions, activities & resources, key stakeholders, customers, users, costs & revenues, metrics & impacts)
		6. Number of (different) services offered by the living lab (e.g., stakeholder engagement) covering (all) different phases of the innovation cycle
	Culture & Collaboration	7. Presence of internal & external business & client relation management process/strategy (including contracts)
		8. Frequency of internal communication & results sharing to keep partners informed & aligned
		9. Number of regional, national & international collaborations beyond the scope of an individual living lab project
Operations	Human Resources	10. % of Implementation of needed internal roles and responsibilities within the operational living lab team in a flexible way (are all roles sufficiently attributed depending on the size of the operational living lab team)
	Operations	11. Time spent within successfully completed projects and/or activities related to the living lab (how many weeks/months/years of experience does the living lab has in running projects and/or activities)
		12. Completeness & frequency of internal self-monitoring processes (how often is the living lab monitoring essential parts of their organization: strategic, financial, equipment & infrastructure, policy, project outcomes)
	Equipment & infrastructure	13. % accessibility in time to facilities (e.g., offices, co-creation spaces, testing facilities...)
		14. % accessibility in time to hard- & software (e.g., co-creation materials, computers, wearables, interaction software, polling/survey software...)
	Openness	

	Innovation partnerships, projects & processes	16. % of implementation of needed processes to safeguard an ethical approach (e.g., regulatory requirements, data protection needed, etc.)
	Ownership of results	17. % of implementation of needed rules & regulations regarding the use, sharing & licensing of data and IP of collaborative outcomes
Users & reality	User centrality	19. % of diversity of stakeholders involved as end-users in living lab projects and/or activities
		20. Degree of influence end-users exerts on the different phases of the innovation cycle (from informing to empowerment)
	Lifecycle & real-life	21. Degree of involvement of end-users in the different phases of the innovation cycle e.g., problem space, solution space, implementation space...)
		22. Degree of use of real-life contexts of users in the different phases of the innovation cycle
	Tools & methods	23. Degree of appropriateness of tools & methods used for the different phases of the innovation cycle
		24. Frequency of external communication & results sharing to keep end-users and external stakeholders informed and engaged
Impact & value	Co-created values	25. % Satisfaction of users/stakeholders (from the whole value chain) concerning their involvement/influence on the innovation cycle
		26. Frequency of knowledge sharing (including results) with relevant (internal & external) stakeholders from the value chain
		27. Number of relevant (open) educational resources (including datasets, trainings) shared/provided for relevant stakeholders
		28. % Satisfaction of users/stakeholders concerning knowledge sharing & capacity building (learning materials & infrastructures)
	Impacts	29. Completeness & frequency of impact assessments (how often is the living lab monitoring different types of impacts they are generating: societal, environmental, economic, regulatory, academic)
Stability & harmonization	Stability	30. % Increase in number of relationships (with a reliable partner network and customers)
		31. Level of financial sustainability based on a balanced & diversified set of fundings (structural vs. project-based) & revenue streams
		32. Number of living lab value propositions, flexible to adapt to new circumstances
	Harmonization & scale-up	33. % Increase in number of partners committed to scale up products/solutions/services developed by the living lab
		34. Number of products/solutions/services (able to be) scaled-up

		35. Number of participation in (cross-border/cross-sectoral) initiatives/projects based on harmonized living lab infrastructures, standards, skills, methods, tools processes or services
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4.4.4 Research and Innovation process

This tool offers a graphical depiction of the Living Lab Research and Innovation process, catering to external researchers and research teams interested in conducting research within a Living Lab environment. Its purpose is to assist them in identifying the necessary steps to undertake. Once the initial Touchpoints (highlighted in the blue column) have been identified, researchers can then follow the process guidelines while maintaining open and effective communication with the respective Living Lab throughout their research activities.

4.5 PART 3. Research process

The table below presents the Living Lab research process phases and details about the services that Living Labs can offer in each phase. These phases are inspired by research in the Health and Wellbeing domain but can be extended to other domains as well.

Table 9 Living Lab Research phases

Phases	Research process steps	Related living lab services
Planning phase	1. Identifying the research problem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use living lab capacity building services to gain knowledge and skills to conduct your own living lab study. Conduct small pre-study with a living lab. Use e.g., co-creation sessions or expert opinion services to gain better understanding of the research topic or to formulate robust research design. Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping with living lab to determine suitable sample.
	2. Conduct literature review and collect other relevant background information	
	3. Formulate research questions and/or hypothesis	

	4. Define the research design and determine sample	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use open data repository and omit data collection entirely or partially.
Preparation phase	Acquire funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply temporary living lab research funding if it is available e.g., via open call. Utilize living lab grant writing and funding application support services or join to consortium who is applying funding. Use living lab networking services to gain access with funders.
	Research infrastructure selection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get in contact with a living lab and familiarize yourself with their research infrastructure key assets and service offerings. Living lab research infrastructure covers single-sited, distributed, virtual access and mobility facilities, which each have different strengths. Clarify your research needs in intake and matching process with potential living lab infrastructure providers. Wait for their offer. Send equipment and/or facility rental request to a living lab.
	Ethic approval	Living lab will prepare and manage ethical application process for your study.
	Participant recruitment	Living lab will use their stakeholder population repository to recruit study participants for the study.
Implementation phase	5. Data collection	Living lab will conduct data collection according to research protocol and will manage the project for you. You will benefit from wide range available methods, tools, devices, technologies, validated questionnaires and instruments, which can be tailored to your research needs.
	6. Analyze data	Living lab will conduct data analysis if agreed in project contract. Translations or summary reports from local language to English are made if there isn't common language between customer and collected data.
	7. Interpret results	Discuss and interpret result in a co-creative manner with diverse group of experts from living lab innovation ecosystem.
	8. Write research report	Co-author scientific and professional publications with living lab researchers.
Dissemination and valorisation	9. Disseminate findings	Utilize living lab sales, marketing and networking services to disseminate and valorise your research results to various stakeholder groups. Gain visibility by sharing your publication in living lab publication repository.

4.6 PART 4. Innovation process

This Table presents the Living Lab innovation process phases with detailed information about the activities performed at each stage. The Living Lab Innovation process stems from the TRL levels of innovation process.

Table 10 Living Lab innovation process phases

Title	Research environment	Solution name	Functionality, Interactivity	Solution maturity	Exploratory research aim	Confirmatory research aim
TRL 1: Need assessment and ideation	Laboratory	Idea	None	A group of needs, problems, opportunities and/or ideas identified. Not been proven feasible.	Investigate a problem or topic to generate new ideas and hypotheses.	Prioritize needs and ideas.
TRL 2: Concept co-creation	Laboratory	Visual prototype	None, or very limited	High-level speculative and static concept transforming to concept prototype without or very limited functionality. Focuses on explaining and describing overall design concept and user interactions. Based on sketches, diagrams, drawings, compositions, mock-ups, wireframes, digital models, storyboards	Investigate a topic in more detailed to co-create and formulate concept and value hypotheses in iterative or parallel manner.	Prioritize options to determine the most appropriate way to proceed with further development.
TRL 3: Proof-of-concept (POC)	Laboratory	Alpha prototype	Very limited		Explore different human, technical, economic, and environmental aspect to verify what is the best approach to develop the solution.	Test value hypothesis and confirm or reject them. Focus on user acceptance and feasibility.

				, paper interface and/or descriptive text. Non interactive to very limited interactivity.		
TRL 4: Prototyping in lab	Laboratory		Limited	User experience / working prototypes transforming from low to moderate depth and breadth of functionality . First working models to identify and	Co-create rapid functional prototype versions. Focus on the basic functionalities.	Verify usability, and technical feasibility to find out the most promising options having highest cost/profit ratio and user acceptance.
TRL 5: Prototyping in relevant environment	Relevant		Moderate	resolve usability, design and technical issues. Can have substantial flaws or missing functions.	Continue to iteratively refine the prototype based on the collected feedback and co-creation inputs.	Validate that prototype as a whole and at component / subsystem level is working and performs as expected while meeting the predictions.
TRL 6: Demonstration in relevant environment	Relevant	Beta prototype	High or near full	High-fidelity prototype with near fully functionality that closely resemble the final solution and adequately addresses all critical features. Technical feasibility fully		Validate that prototype as a whole can operate reliable and consistently over time and is ready for operational usage.

				demonstrated.		
TRL 7: Small scale demonstration in operational environment	Operational		Near full or full	Production prototype near final solution (or final solution) functioning at system level		By using rigorous evidence-based data validate social/human, economic viability, scalability, positive/negative effects, as well as any unintended consequences or indirect impacts that may arise in operational environment. Start in small scale and increase the scale gradually to full scale.
TRL 8: Full scale demonstration in operational environment	Operational	Pilot prototype	Full	Final complete solution at system level.	Refine and commit to final solution.	
TRL 9: Post market testing / surveillance	Operational	Final solution	Full	Final complete solution at system level ready for sale.	Refinement via versioning strategy.	Monitor and evaluate safety, effectiveness, performance and quality over longer period of time.

4.7 PART 5. R&D Services

R&D services refer to a group of common R&D services, which a Living Lab can offer to its customers during the different Living Lab R&D process phases. Each service combines one or more data collection approaches or other activities. R&D Services are parts of the Living Lab standard needed to accomplish a Living Lab R&D project as a whole or part of it. Each service description defines the type of service and additional details related to service delivery such as technical and functional quality. Living lab R&D services are classified into the following categories:

1. Testing and validation
2. Community and network building
3. Project planning and management
4. Co-creation
5. Capacity building

6. Advisory services
7. Market and sales support
8. Infrastructure and data management

It is noted that some of the services can be included in multiple categories.

Table 11 Services categorization, inputs and outputs

Input	PoV	Service	Output	Category
Application	client	Temporary research funding	funding decision	supporting
Course enrolment	client	Capacity building	skills and capabilities increased/ knowledge about LLS	supporting
Request/application	client	Equipment and facility rental	tender and usage of equipment	R&D
Research idea/contact from the network	client	Grant writing	grant application	supporting
Call search	LL	Call identification	targeted calls	back office
Request/application	client	Public procurement applicant support	help meet the tendering criteria/process	supporting
Request/application	client	Public authority procurement support	defining market dialogue/innovative procurement	supporting
Application with information about goal/data	client	Access to data	data	R&D
Idea/offer request with info about topic	client	Intake and matching	understanding client's request/requirement	supporting
New and existing contacts	LL	Innovation network orchestration	partner and collaboration network	back office
Network contacts and	LL	Panel management	repository of stakeholders	back office

Project plan/research protocol	LL/client	Participant recruitment	study participants	supporting/R&D
Project plan/research protocol	client	Stakeholders and partner analysis and mapping	identification of relevant stakeholders and/or study participants	supporting/R&D
Project plan/research protocol	client	Expert opinions and advisory services	expert opinion	supporting/R&D
Research plan/input from previous R&D activities	client	Co-creation session	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/input from previous R&D activities	client	Usability testing	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/input from previous R&D activities	client	Concept and proof-of-concept	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/input from previous R&D activities	client	Clinical trials	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/input from previous R&D activities	client	Idea selection and testing	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/input from previous R&D activities	client	Large-scale real-life testing and piloting	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/input from previous R&D activities	client	Prototyping test	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/input from previous R&D activities	client	Simulation test	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/input from previous R&D activities	client	Small-scale real-life testing and piloting	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/input from previous R&D activities	client	Foresighting (trends, weak	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D

		signals and wild cards)		
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Competitor and market analysis benchmarking	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Impact assessment and validation test	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Idea/offer request with info about topic	client	Marketing and sales support	sales lead	supporting
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Legal, regulation and safety standard support	outcomes/report of the session/data	supporting/R&D

Depending on the nature and the scope of each service, the structure and the elements of the descriptive information vary. Below, follows a brief explanation of the R&D services structure:

Table 12 R&D services structure

Section	Description
Description	In the description field a general overview of the service is given (e.g., definition, scope, followed processes etc.)
R&D service categories	Here it is indicated the category (or categories) to which belongs the service
Key characteristics in living lab context	In this field are highlighted the most important points/aspects of the service in a Living Lab framework
Pre-tasks	By pre-tasks we mean the several steps that are considered important to be completed before the delivery of the service
Participants' role	Participants' role refers to the particular actions/activities that are expected to be achieved by the stakeholders during the service delivery

Objectives	In this part are identified the various goals that are envisaged to be accomplished during the delivery of the service
Methods	This field refers to the methodology that stakeholders could follow for the service implementation (e.g., focus groups, training sessions, workshops, seminars, presentations, interviews etc.)
Tools	By tools we mean the specific instruments which could be possibly exploited during the service (e.g., questionnaires, sensors, Teams meeting, Zoom, whiteboards etc.)
Process phase	Here it is indicated the phase or stage during which the service is usually delivered

4.7.1 Expert opinion, and advisory services

Description: Expert(s) who have long-standing practical and/or scientific experience in the field of enquiry provide(s) a well-founded written or oral answer for your questions, including the ethics domain/ethics guidelines, and offer(s) advisory services on the use of specific equipment. Expert(s) are discussing ideas and problems from a different angle to respectfully challenge, test and refine ideas (e.g., as devil’s advocate looking for problems). Qualified and traceable arguments in favor of and against a specific position in an applied issue to support decision-making and development activities. Professional work is a paid service, but “consultation” can be a free of charge service. In most cases it is done by Living Lab on its own, hosting organization personnel, subcontractor.

R&D service category-ies: Project planning and management, Capacity building, Advisory services, Market and sales support

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Typically consists of one-to-one relationship between the customer and the expert but may include opinions from multiple experts.
- Internal or external experts (local, national and international experts)
- Multidisciplinary collaboration/Pool of experts

Objectives:

- Offer advice on UX or usability studies,
- Consulting care solutions (ICT and devices), in specific/narrow fields in which Living Lab has experts (e.g., energy consumption calculations),
- Consulting on consent and ethics requirement and processes,
- Consulting technical solutions (ICT, medical and other devices, sensors, wearables, health apps, machine learning, medical engineering)
- Consulting legal issues, networking and contacting people (e.g., doctors, academia, pharmacy, healthcare professionals, policy makers, local ecosystem actors), research ideas,
- Innovation management, interventions,
- Creation of training materials and processes

Methods: One to one and group discussion, advisory board, expert identification

Tools/Online tools: ethical tools, training materials

4.7.2 Idea selection and testing

Description: Idea testing is a low-cost and quick process in which high-level ideas are selected (i.e., ranked) or tested with real end-users via different methods such as interviews, surveys or during the workshop. In order to conduct idea testing, different high-level ideas are pre-described in written or in visual format, and then communicated to the real end-users or experts. The main aim is to collect feedback on the already existing idea proposal. Feedback can also include improvement suggestions.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation, Co-creation

Objectives:

- Collect feedback, prioritize ideas or different alternative options,
- Lowering development risk by selecting the best/most promising idea for further development,
- Challenge the ideas from different perspectives

Methods: Co-creation workshop, interviews, focus groups, surveys, questionnaires, small group discussions, informal talks

4.7.3 Co-creation session

Description: Co-creation session is a facilitated group activity to find solutions for a specific problem by gathering ideas, solutions and insights from workshop participants while using variety of methods. Depending on the workshop focus, it may comprise ideation, concept development and testing. Typical duration for short workshop is from 45 minutes to 90 minutes, medium-length workshop from 90 minutes to 3 hours, and long-workshop from 3 hours to 1 day. The number of participants may vary depending on how many facilitators are available, and what kind of working methods are utilized. Typically, a workshop facilitated by a single facilitator consists of six to eight persons. Number of participants are sometimes numbered to enable them to work in pairs.

R&D service category-ies: Co-creation, Capacity building

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Fundamental features: Requires (1) facilitator(s), (2) interaction/is interactive, (3) iterative process
- Can be applied in almost all phases: e.g., ideation, concept creation/testing, prototyping, prototype testing
- Can be virtual/online or in person event
- It is a service but also a generic method
- Duration varies, but usually 2-3 hours
- Often multi-stakeholder approach: researchers, clinicians, students (e.g., paediatric project, project on language and communication). Depending on the concept all actors of the quadruple helix are contacted, number of users depends also on the stakeholders. Engagement of different stakeholders can also be achieved by running series of sessions

Participants' role:

- In the beginning of the innovation process, involve the users as the creators
- If there is a product with higher Technology Readiness Level (TRL), a ready Minimum Viable Product (MVP) is more like a focus group,
- Need finding session, focus group is more of an evaluation,

Pre-tasks: prepare session upfront with the sketches, if focus group - open questions (sent beforehand), workshop preparation template

Objectives (varies depending on researchers' interest):

- Co-creation session: Finding solutions for a specific problem with or without prototypes or mock-ups. Co-creating the actual design, sketch interfaces, make the solution tangible, Drafting (prototypes, drawing), mock-ups
- Demo-session: specifically, setup to explain about the use of a prototype or market ready product and gather (first) feedback. Often done before launching a test.
- Business model session (broader, a service?): developing and defining a business model (e.g., potential customers, sales channels, distributors, value chain, the Willingness to Pay, revenue streams etc.

Methods: Brainstorming, use simulations, group discussion / focus groups, semi-structured focus group, survey, questionnaire

Tools: Projection walls, visual mock-ups, use tangible tools for prototyping (e.g., wearables), team groups, polling (tech); questionnaires, focus groups, idea generation techniques, post-it notes, creative supplies, art supplies,

Online tools: Online system for idea generation, Teams meeting, Zoom with breakout rooms, Google meet, Miro whiteboard, Mural.co

4.7.4 Impact assessment and validation test

Description: Impact assessment is a formal, evidence-based procedure that assesses the total outcome that comes as a result of the tested activity, above and beyond what would have happened anyway. Depending on the duration and scope of the validation process impact can be evaluated on individuals, organizations and the society in the short, medium and long term. Validation is the documented act of demonstration that a product or a service will consistently lead to the expected results. Validation test ensures that the product or the service actually meets the defined requirements and demonstrates that the solution fulfils its intended use when deployed on appropriate real environment.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- The validation test is usually designed by LL
- Validation testing has to meet some minimum TRL level in order reliable test the solution impact

Objectives:

- Verify that the developed solution will consistently lead to the expected results and meet defined requirement
- Evaluate social impact
- Quantify change after solution usage

Methods: Survey, observation, pre and post measurement (short and long term), quantitative measures (e.g., physiological measures), feasibility study, usability study, interviews

Tools/online tools: Questionnaires, validated scientific scale/questionnaires, sensors, thermal cameras

4.7.5 Concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study

Description: Concept test is a low cost and quick process in which a high-level concept is tested with real end-users via different methods such as interviews and surveys. In order to conduct a concept test, preliminary concept description must exist in written or visual format, which is then communicated to the real end-users or experts. The main aim is to collect feedback for the initial concept proposal and its possible variations. Concept test can also include a feasibility study, which also covers technical, economic, legal, operational and scheduling issues relating the proposed concept. In all, concept-testing phase verifies if a concept has market interest, while feasibility study

shows if the product or service based on concept can be developed. Collected feedback also includes improvement suggestions.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation, Co-creation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Core service in LL

Participants' role: Two main actors (projects and companies), joint work among Living Labs and interested partners/stakeholders

Process phase: After concept co-creation

Objectives:

- Verify if a concept has market or research interest,
- Testing early “prototypes” to get feedback for development, identify improvement suggestions,
- Concept feasibility test focuses on verifying if concept can be technically/economically done (preliminary assessment),
- Provide development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs, identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests, personalized in the client need and varies case by case

Methods: Survey, demo-session, interview, Wizard of Oz

Tools: Paper prototype, visual dummies close to final (visual UI), visual VR can be used to test-multitasking (real work), long term evaluations, interviews, questionnaires

4.7.6 Innovation network orchestration

Description: Establishing productive working relationship between existing and previously unconnected but complementary actor parties and helping them (companies, public health and other sector, academia, and end-user stakeholders) to work together properly and well. Handling conflicts and supporting interactions.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building, Capacity building

Objectives:

- Establish new collaboration relationships,
- Promote Living Lab methodology and raising awareness,
- Lobbying Living Lab movement

Methods: Events, seminars, webinars, conferences, one-to-one meetings, site visits, publications (scientific and professional), memberships in local/regional/national/international associations/networks

4.7.7 Large-scale real-life testing and piloting

Description: Similar to small-scale testing but with a longer duration or larger number of test participants who are representing the real end-users of the target group. During piloting, the aim is to evaluate the full scale and near or fully functional product(s) or service(s) at the system level in real environment with real end-users to make sure that the solution is scalable. Includes often impact assessment and validation testing.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Usually, the aim of the testing defines the number of participants
- Sometimes, for large numbers the LL can hire a specialized company for support

Objectives:

- Evaluate scalability,
- Evaluate system level impact and functionality,

Methods: Testing in real-life setting with real users, longitudinal study, sensors, interview, survey, observation, ethnographic studies, diaries, qualitative/quantitative methods, pre and post measurement

4.7.8 Prototyping test

Description: Prototyping test is a low cost and quick process in which a product or service with limited functionality and interaction is tested with real end-users. An interactive prototype product or service must be available so real end-users or experts can experience it. This prototype test can be, for instance, an interactive mock-up of a web service, which interface looks like a real thing. One can navigate through different screens and see simulated content. Also, the service prototype can consist of role-playing exercise to simulate service encounters. The main aim is to collect feedback on a 'close to real' user experience as possible, but at a lower cost. Different methods such as interviews, surveys and observations can be used.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- From rapid prototyping to the MVP
- IT solutions/Physical and cognitive exercises

Objectives:

- Similar to proof-of-concept but testing higher fidelity solution,
- Identify improvement suggestions and usability test,
- Provides development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,
- Identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests

Methods: Survey, observation, demo-session, interview, Wizard of Oz, usability tests, role playing

Tools: Paper prototype, wireframes, interactive mock-ups, scaled down prototypes, visual dummies close to final (visual UI), video recording, usability questionnaires, eye tracking

4.7.9 Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation

Description: A small-scale real-life experiment is a small-scale and short-term preliminary study conducted to evaluate feasibility of the suggested product or service and to improve it based on the testing result. Testing includes a small number of test participants who are representing the real end-users of the target group.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context

- Usually lab-based studies
- Can mostly involve qualitative feedback
- Testing quality and user satisfaction,

Objectives:

- Verify that the developed solution will work also in real-life setting,
- Evaluate usability before engaging more people in testing,

Methods: Testing in real-life setting with real users, survey, interview, survey, observation, diaries, qualitative/quantitative methods, pre and post measurement

Tools: Validated questionnaires, sensors

4.7.10 Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping

Description: Identifying groups, organizations, and people who are relevant stakeholders. Prioritizing and ranking stakeholders based on their perspectives and interest. Mapping the relationship between different stakeholders and company objectives. Deliverable(s) Written report.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building, Project planning and management, Co-creation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context

- Within a research context / for programs and projects.
- Trying to promote a diversity-centered design

Pre-tasks: Searching and listing all the interested stakeholders/partners, contacting them, and then mapping possible contributors

Objectives:

- Identifying relevant/key/negative stakeholders,
- Identify stakeholders' interest,
- Provide information to participant recruitment

Methods: Focus group, workshop, interviews, questionnaires methodology, social network analysis, two-dimensional matrix (e.g., power, influence, interest/need, support/attitude), primary/secondary/tertiary stakeholder, the salience model

Tools: Online whiteboard (e.g., Miro), stakeholder mapping template

4.7.11 Usability testing

Description: Usability testing is a technique used to evaluate a product by testing it in order to give direct input on how real users use or would use the product or service. Usability inspection is conducted when a professional evaluator inspects a user interface and gives an expert opinion regarding the usability. This approach does not involve real user. Usability testing with real users includes real users who have no prior exposure to the product or service. In the context of Living Labs is mostly provided real user testing.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Objectives: Identify usability problems, provides development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,

Methods: Moderated/unmoderated, remote/in-person, comparative testing, open ended explorative testing, user satisfaction, phone/video interview, usability lab testing, session recordings, observation

Tools: SUS, QUEST, feasibility assessment and other several tests, eye-tracking camera

4.7.12 Capacity building

Description: Training, knowledge sharing and awareness raising, site visits and event arrangement. Offering training for end-users and/or practitioners to improve their skills and knowledge about Living Lab approach, co-creation, iterative development and healthcare and wellbeing market. Stimulating knowledge sharing and awareness raising by publishing professional and scientific publications and arranging events, site visits and seminars.

R&D service category-ies: Capacity building

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- The way of knowledge sharing and transfer depends on the project and on the purpose
- Use of short-term or long-term methods and courses
- Material can be both created for a purpose but also some available online

Participants' role:

- Service beneficiaries become trainees
- Living Labs can offer support for the design and facilitation of capacity building programs

Methods: Co-creation methodology, focus groups, training sessions (tech & non-tech), ethical training & legal in large scale settings, seminars, presentations, workshops, webinars, forums, websites and web-engines, events, site visits, publications, summer schools, degree program, methodological training, how to use new product

4.7.13 Living Lab project planning and management

Description: Planning project goals, costs, schedule, list of deliverables, delivery dates and resources. Written project plan for one or multiple innovation stages is made. In the project management, planned tasks are completed by executing, monitoring, controlling, and closing the work of a project team to achieve specific goals and to meet specific success criteria at the specified time.

R&D service category-ies: Project planning and management

Objectives:

- Successful development and implementation of all project procedures,
- Supervision and quality control,
- Internal/external communication,
- Optimization of the allocated resources,
- Getting clients and funding,

Tools/Online tools: Project and planning management tools, Microsoft Teams, Microsoft Excel, email, phone, messaging application

4.7.14 Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking

Description: Quantitative and qualitative methods are used to evaluate the size of the market both, in volume and in value (also known as market studies). Customer segments, buying patterns, competition, and the economic environment are defined to identify the regulations and the barriers to entry. Defining the market by listing and describing current, future, direct and indirect competitors and analysing their competitive offering (e.g., SWOT) and user experience. Comparing offerings by measuring the performance of the developed products, services, or processes against those, which are considered to be the best in the industry. Can consist also of literature reviews to a search and evaluation of the available scientific or professional body of knowledge for the given subject or chosen topic area.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services, Market and sales support

Participants' role: Competitors or stakeholders interested in collaborations, can be done by students or experts.

Objectives:

- Identify the “space” for innovation, not analysing only specific segments, but also looking for new opportunities
- Analyse market acceptance, support scalability and transferability potential, focus can be domestic/international/global market,
- Identify direct and/or indirect competitors, qualitative or quantitative description of the market, focus can also be in research context or innovation management practices

Methods: Desk research, acquiring the information from the experts in the field, following the market as a job profile/duty, the people working know specific segments/areas, bibliometric studies, literature reviews to a search and evaluate of the available scientific or professional body of knowledge for the given subject or chosen topic area, technology exploitation, market analysis, benchmarking, other methods combined with interview(s) with a leading reference organisation or expert(s), assessment of technologies, knowledge syntheses (systematic and scoping reviews), evaluations methods of intervention (ETMI method), workshops and sessions, measures of satisfaction of users

Tools: SWOT analysis, business model canvas, Innovation management standard (CEN/TS 16555 - covered 7 standards, after ISO 56002:2019)

4.7.15 Intake and matching

Description: During this service, the customer's (e.g., a company, SME, a start-up, a researcher) development and testing needs are clarified for the project planning purposes. It also includes the process of mapping the customer's needs and co-designing of the strategic planning in relation to the target/purpose of the project and Living Lab capabilities to offer the particular project.

R&D service category-ies: Community & Network building, Co-creation, Advisory services

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Can be both open discussion or more focused
- Usually at the beginning of the research process
- Can be virtual/online or in person event
- Duration varies-30 minutes (very short form) to few hours or days. In most of the cases there are multiple meetings taking place/more than one contact
- Often multi-stakeholder approach: Researchers, clinicians, customers, students

Participants' role:

- Customers as co-creators

Pre-tasks:

- Discuss and understand who the customers are and what their needs are.
- Agree to a plan -usually it is made a document/contract- (set goals, explore the different services, engage the operational team
- Revise & follow-up activities with the customer

Objectives

- Make a project proposal/offer between the relevant stakeholders
- Make a project contract

Methods:

Client's needs elicitation methodology, interview/focus group/questionnaires for defining the project and collecting the needs, co-design of the strategic planning in relation to the target/purpose of the project

4.7.16 Simulation test

Description: Simulation is a technique that creates a situation and environment, which allows end-users to experience a representation of a real event in a risk-free environment. A predefined simulation scenario defines a particular set of conditions to resemble authentic situations in a location where a simulation experience takes place to test and to gain understanding of tested solution and

related human interactions. After simulation event, facilitators and end-users re-examine the simulation experience, and various aspects of the completed simulation are discussed.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context

- Mainly for ICT solutions
- Simulation labs, smart home that simulate real-life home/specific scenarios to simulate real space

Objectives:

- Simulate real-life situations and behavior but lower cost,
- Identify improvement suggestions and usability test,
- Provide development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,
- Identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests

Methods: Simulation test, virtual reality (VR), usage scenarios, interview, debriefing, observation, survey, Wizard of Oz, sensors, usage logs, hospital ward, interactive patient mannequin, usage scenarios,

Tools: Audio recording, video recording

4.7.17 Clinical trials

Description: Clinical trials are experiments or observations done to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of new solution by monitoring its effects on large groups of people. Subjects are typically divided into two or more groups, one having “real treatment” by using the developed solution and the other group(s) using tried-and-true solution or not using any solution. The results are compared between the groups to evaluate the impacts.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Clinical trials are similar to impact assessment and validation test activities but follow more strict validation and approval process.

Participants' role:

- Customers as co-creators

Objectives

- To find out if new solutions are safe and effective
- Get official approval for new solution

Methods:

- Has multiple phases and classes which depend on the developed solution

4.7.18 Grant writing and funding application support service

Description: Offering tailored support by identifying the proper local, regional, national and international funding instruments, helping to write and manage a funding application process including finding the right partners for the project if needed. In most cases a Living Lab will become a project partner, but it can also be provided as a paid service without participation.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services

Objectives:

- Acquiring/providing funding for “customer” to execute a Living lab project or buy Living Lab services,
- Getting project partner for a Living Lab project

4.7.19 Panel management

Description: Panel is a pre-existing group of pre-screened people (e.g. patients, practitioners etc.) who have given their consent to take part in different research activities over an agreed period. Panel members have given their contact details and other profiling information, which enables fast recruitment for specific research activities as they come up.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building, Project planning and management, Advisory services, Infrastructure and data management

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Group of patients, students but also experts, experts by experience and other staff can be used as a panel (agreement is necessary in every case)
- Having engagement procedures in place (win to win situation), social activities

Objectives:

- Enable fast participant recruitment,
- Lower the management effort (no need to fill profile information multiple times)

Method: survey, recruitment collaboration with medical professionals (e.g., in hospital ward)

Tools/Online tools: intake questionnaire, phone, open calls in social media/web, posters, email, personal invitations

4.7.20 Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing

Description: Post-market surveillance is a “real world” test of medical innovations in patient subgroups. It is a practice of monitoring the safety of a medical innovation after it has been released on the market. Market acceptance testing focuses on collecting market feedback for the next revision development and tracking the solution performance in real competitive market conditions.

R&D service category-ies: Market and sales support

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Usually within a clinical or community research context (within the context of specific projects/the products that come out as research outcomes) and not as a standalone service.
- As normal customer feedback collection and health promotion, for continuum improvement of the tool

Objectives:

- Monitoring the safety of a medical innovation after it has been released on the market,
- Evaluate social impact,
- Identify new opportunities for business and research

Methods: Survey, observation, interviews, helpdesk logs, technical logs, complain reports, pre and post measurement (long term), market studies

Tools/online tools: questionnaires, validated scientific scale/questionnaires, sensors

4.7.21 Temporary research funding

Description: Providing funding (or an investment) for research, product and business development for small and medium-sized companies or start-ups. Typically, funding is targeted for short-term small-scale experiments or if an externally funded project has resources for this kind of activity (e.g.,

open calls). Also, it can be done in collaboration with local research centers, publicly funded “development companies” and networks or similar.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services

Objectives:

- Providing funding to execute small scale Living Lab project (e.g., testing)

Methods: Offering funds within funded projects for small-scale testing or co-creation

4.7.22 Access to data

Description: Referring to service, which enables customers to access or retrieve data from one or more databases consisting of relevant data, based on mutual agreements respecting ethics and GDPR, which can be used for development or testing purposes.

R&D service categories: Testing and validation, Market and sales support, Infrastructure and data management

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Usually 2 sources: already existing data, new data collected
- Data must be anonymized and encrypted
- Consent from participants have been previously acquired by the LLs when it's required by ethical and legal legislations
- Type of data: demographics/personal data, health-clinical data (e.g., cognitive, treatment changes, physical performance, care to rehabilitation), measure data, sensors' data (brain activity)
- For open data, FAIR data principles should be followed
- Ethical approval and GDPR processes when needed

Pre-tasks:

- Create a database to store data
- Define the accessibility of the database (public or limited access) and how data are collected (in an integrated way or occasional/ad hoc databases/infrastructures)
- It is, usually, needed a request that is passed to the responsible of databases

4.7.23 Marketing and sales support

Description: Providing marketing and sales support for 1) making right contacts by giving business contacts, sales and business leads, 2) setting up and arranging meetings and events, 3) showcasing products and services in a showroom or giving online/onsite visibility in Living Lab own communication channels, 4) providing “user approved” certification, and 5) offering soft landing support to help to set up business in given Living Lab country or region.

R&D service category-ies: Market and sales support

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- It can be introductory to healthcare companies and service providers and goes up to the point of developing a BM

Objectives:

- Finding right contacts and customers for Living Lab clients,

Tools: “user approved” certification, showroom, showcasing, business meetings, interviews, events, soft landing services, sales/business leads

4.7.24 Public procurement support services

Description: Public procurement (e.g., related to research activities) is governed by EU and national rules. Support with public contract issues and the public procurement process is given to help clients to meet the tendering criteria and/or join the tendering process. Also helping public authorities to establish market dialogue when developing the public procurement announcement. This includes Pre-Commercial Procurement and innovative procurement processes.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Pre-commercial procurement, innovative procurement, public procurement
- Project based
- Validation Software (integration) - Hardware (operational validation in real environment)
- Legal design and decision-making support

Methods: Planning process based on co-creation, pre-commercial procurement (PCP), innovative procurement

4.7.25 Equipment and facility rental service

Description: Offering equipment, labs, spaces, human resources and other facilities for rent. Some Living Labs do this based on a win-to-win agreement where money does not change hand. Also, some Living Labs require research collaboration when renting.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and Validation, Co-creation, Advisory services, Infrastructure and data management

Participants' role: In some cases, researchers can visit the LL and use the provided facilities free of charge

Objectives:

- Getting temporary human, space, technical or other facility resources,
- Enable research collaboration

Methods: Payment, research collaboration grounded on Living Lab resources

Tools: Simulation lab

4.7.26 Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)

Description: Foresighting is a practice of exploring expected and alternative futures. Trend is a general tendency or direction evident from past events increasing or decreasing in strength of frequency of observation. A weak signal is an indicator of a potentially emerging issue that may become significant in the future. "Wild card" is a high-impact event that seem too incredible or is considered too unlikely to happen; yet many do happen.

R&D service category-ies: Market and sales support

Objectives:

- Policy consulting,
- Create a future vision,
- Identify new opportunities and risks,

Methods: Back casting, brainstorming, user/citizen panels, workshop/session, expert panel, interview, literature review, role playing, scenarios, survey, SWOT, wild card & weak signals, science fiction/crazy ideas

4.7.27 Legal, regulation and safety standard support

Description: Providing support to navigate to the legal, regulatory and safety standard requirements and help planning to meet the requirements.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Legal design and decision-making support
- Support on signed agreements, protocol
- In some cases, external contractors for IPR, RGDP

Objectives:

- Similar to expert opinion and advisory services but focusing on legal and regulatory issues

4.8 PART 6. Living lab research infrastructure

In regulation 1291/2013, the EU Parliament and Council of the EU define Research Infrastructure (RI) as “facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields”. Living lab RIs consist

- **Single-sited facility:** Unified single body of equipment at one physical location
 - Laboratory or smart home
- **Distributed facility:** Facilities, resources and services that are geographically scattered in multiple location
 - City, city district, outdoor space (e.g., nature/hiking trails)
 - sensor networks, network of homes
- **Virtual access-based facility:** Resources and services that are exclusively available via online internet-based tools.
 - Access and ability storage scientific data and repositories, tools for virtual collaboration, various computer services,
- **Mobile facility:** Facilities and resources which can be easily moved to from one place to another
 - Handheld devices and non-handheld equipment

4.9 PART 7A. Methods and tools

This section includes two templates that can be used as a tool for the designing and reporting of co-creation sessions within the LLs. In particular, the first template consists of several parts that are crucial for thoroughly describing the design and the implementation of a co-creation session and the second one includes the information considered important for reporting it. In addition, this section encompasses three distinct Ethics Tools, namely a protocol template designed for co-creation activities, another protocol template tailored for intervention studies, and a third template for Data Sharing Agreement / Joint-Controller Agreement.

4.9.1 Template for designing a co-creation session

CO-CREATION SESSION

JRA (Joint research activity) x

Small-case study name:

Co-creation session with: (e.g., care professionals, patients, informal carers)

General recommendations:

The objectives and scenarios can be split up: e.g.: 1 session for care professionals & 1 session for patients/informal carers etc. We would advise you to organize separate sessions for professionals and patients/informal carers and also, to adjust and fill the template separately for each group. The set-up is quite similar, but the focus is sometimes different. It is suggested a min of 4 participants and a max of 12. If wanted, you can video tape, as a back-up (*attention to the ethics considerations – videotaping should be included into the consent form).

Other recommendations:

- o Delay erodes quality
- o Debriefing and reflection with the team (moderator and observer) improves quality
- o Keep the research questions in mind
- o Stick as close to the data as possible (quotes, words used by participants)

RESEARCH QUESTIONS & AIM

Describe the research questions and the objectives of the co-creation session, depending on your target group and the information you want to collect.

*Some general research questions can be the same across the different regions, to be able to compare and report some results later on.

e.g.:

Session with health care professionals	Session with participants (e.g., older adults)
What is their current experience with (intervention) technology?	What experiences do the participants have from previous... (possible benefits, difficulties)?
To what extend is technology accepted by the clinicians? (attitude towards technology)	To what extend is the use of technology accepted by the participants for supporting... (benefits, challenges)?
What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during...?	What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during ...?
How do they follow up on their patients?	

*Please structure and enumerate your research questions in order to be easier to report the answers afterwards (Report template: section “Output summary & main findings”).

STAKEHOLDERS

Define all the stakeholders of your co-creation session

- The number of facilitators
- The number of observers/documenters
- The number of participants

STRUCTURE & PLANNED ACTIVITIES

Define the structure of your co-creation session(s), the activities you are planning to include (e.g., open discussions based on pre-defined questions, brainstorming, demonstration of a selected tool)

GUIDING QUESTIONS

Define the questions you are planning to ask to the participants.

*Please structure and enumerate your questions in order to be easier to report the answers afterwards (Report template: section “Output summary & main findings”)

*Some overall questions can be the same for a general part across the small-scale studies within the JRAs.

e.g.:

Session with health care professionals

Research question	Guiding questions
What is their current experience with (intervention) technology?	From your previous experience, are there any technological means that are exploited during...? Do you personally use any kind of technology for supporting...?/How do you use technology?
To what extent is technology accepted (attitude towards technology)?	Are you open to use technology? Are your patients open to use technology?
What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during...?	Are there any difficulties or challenges that you think it's possible to encounter when using technological means during...? Is there anything that you would like to be different or that could be improved?
How do they follow up on their patients?	

Session with participants (e.g., older adults)

Research question	Guiding questions
What experiences do the participants have from the use of technology so far (possible benefits, difficulties)?	Do you use any kind of technology in...?/ What are your experiences from previous (challenges, benefits)...? What kind of support you think is needed for you to use technology in...?
To what extent is the use of technology accepted by the participants for supporting... (benefits, challenges)?	Are you open and willing to use technology?/ How possible do you think it is for you to use technological means when you...?
What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during ...?	What would be the biggest return for you to use technology during...? Are there any difficulties or challenges that you think it's possible to encounter when using technological means during...?

TOOLS & MATERIAL/RESOURCES

Describe all the tools and materials you are planning to use during your co-creation session(s) (E.g., informed consent to sign for each participant, templates, post-it, pen/pencils, blackboard etc.)

EXPECTED OUTPUTS

Define the expected outcomes of your co-creation session(s) (e.g., current status, needs, challenges, expectations/what is needed to happen in the future)

EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE

Here we will define the common participation questionnaires (one for the participants and one for the LL facilitators) that will be used across the study after the end of the co-creation session.

You will find a proposed questionnaire in the last pages of the report template

PLANNED DATE-TIME, SETTING & AGENDA

Define the date, time, place/setting, as well as the activities and their duration within the co-creation session. Indicate also, who will be engaged in each particular slot of the co-creation session. Define the room set-up (e.g., board room style/round table etc.)

e.g.:

Date: Monday 30 May 2022

Time: 12:00-13:30

Place:

Time	Duration	Activity	Team
12:00	10'	Welcome and registration	all
12:10	10'	Presentation	all
12:20	5'	Split participants into tables	table
12:25	5'	Provide the templates and material	table
12:30	40'	Activities/questions - open discussion	table
13:10	15'	Each team presents briefly what was discussed	all
13:25	5'	Questionnaire	all

4.9.2 Template for reporting a co-creation session

REPORT_CO-CREATION SESSION

LL name	
WP & Small-case study name	
Facilitator(s)	
Observer(s)/documenter(s)	
Date of co-creation session	

Number of participants (total)	
---------------------------------------	--

Facilitator team

List the name and the email of the facilitator(s) and the observers(s)/documenter(s) involved in the session. Indicate their role in the session and their profile (e.g. psychologist, nurse, occupational therapist, physiotherapist, gerontologist etc.)

Participants' profile

Fill in each participant's profile in a different row, checking the appropriate cell.

Serial number	GENDER			Age	PROFILE (define the stakeholders you will engage)		
	Male	Female	Neutral/ Other	Year of birth	Stakeholder 1	Stakeholder 2	Stakeholder 3
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							
6							
7							
8							
9							
10							
11							
12							

	Education level
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D2.6 Standard Version 5

Serial number	ISCED 0: Early childhood education	ISCED 1: Primary education	ISCED 2: Lower secondary education	ISCED 3: Upper secondary education	ISCED 4: Post-secondary non-tertiary education	ISCED 5: Short-cycle tertiary education	ISCED 6: Bachelor's or equivalent level	ISCED 7: Master's or equivalent level	ISCED 8: Doctoral or equivalent level
1									
2									
3									
4									
5									
6									
7									
8									
9									
10									
11									
12									

Serial number	Technology literacy				Previous contact with VITALISE project	
	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced	Excellent	YES	NO
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						
6						
7						
8						
9						
10						
11						
12						

ONLY FOR THE HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS

Serial number	How many years have you been in practice?	What area of speciality do you currently work in (i.e. neurology, musculoskeletal etc.)
1		
2		
3		
4		
5		
6		
7		
8		
9		
10		
11		
12		

Session goals

Briefly describe the objectives of the co-creation session.

List of questions & activities

List and briefly describe the questions / activities that guided the discussion for collecting value insights from the participants.

List of tools and materials used

List and briefly describe the list of tools and materials used during the co-creation session.

Photos

In this section add some photos of the event (5-6). It is nice to have some photos depicting the whole event, e.g., with the tables, hands, materials etc., including also the participants, IF THEY HAVE CONSENTED, (probably blurred *ethics considerations). Also, please try to include some photos that have the VITALISE logo in the background (e.g. from a presentation, a banner).

Questionnaire output

In this Section report the output of the VITALISE participation questionnaire (ANNEX 1). This questionnaire is filled by the participants of the co-creation session. Each participant could write his/her name if he/she wants and the facilitator must report the profile category (older adult, caregiver, clinician) for whom they have provided their names an N/A for those have not.

Profile	1	2	3	4	5
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			

Happiness of the team

This questionnaire is filled by the Living Lab (facilitators) team. The goal is to record possible problems in the procedure, the communication and the assigned work. Each Living Lab should fill only one questionnaire that depicts the average impression of the whole team.

1. Assign a score from 1-5 in each co-creation session:

Co-creation session	
How do you feel about the amount of work assigned to you in this co-creation session?	
How do you feel about the amount of work you did in this co-creation session?	
How do you feel about the quality/value of work you did in this co-creation session?	

2. What would you change? (Free text response)

3. What did you like more? (Free text response)

ANNEX 1

1. How do you feel about this co-creation session?

2. Would you like to be with us in possible next sessions? YES NO

3. What did you like most on this co-creation session?

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

4. What you did not like on this co-creation session?

.....
.....
.....
.....

5. Is there anything you want to propose as a possible improvement?

.....
.....
.....
.....

4.9.3 Ethics tools

4.9.3.1 Protocol template for co-creation activities

(Highlighted text is present to provide examples. Please replace it to correspond to your study)

Research project: [Project Title]

Research Study: [Study Title]

Researchers: [Laboratory 1, Partner 2, Research Center 3]

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1. Introduction

[Provide an introduction, describing the problem (with references), the target population (who faces this problem), contemporary tools that try to address it, their

advantages/disadvantages etc. Also state the objective of the study and how it relates to the descriptions given.

The text below is indicative. Change it as needed.]

One of the most frequently encountered difficulties affecting the [aspect of life], is the [integration/inclusion etc.] of the people [in the target population]. Technological interventions and approaches, in the effort to find a solution, end up being transformed into interventions "from above". Often, therefore, in situations that arise, the needs of people [in the target group] are neglected. An important body of evidence suggests that program designers and programmers have [medium/little or no knowledge] of the challenges that [the target population] faces. [Describe use cases, homogeneity of the target group and existing solutions/methodologies failing to capture them]

In this context, the main objective of the project is:

To gather and utilize interdisciplinary research knowledge and findings that approach the issue of the relationship between [mention the challenges] and [aspect of life]. In this context, it aims to collect data, through spaces of experimentation that provide the potential of action, in order to support [the accessibility/education/interaction etc.] of [the target population], adapting to the individual needs and the necessary settings required for the ["smooth adaptation", "digital transition", etc.] during their [daily/weekly etc.] interaction with [(purpose-specific) software/services].

2. Purpose of study

The purpose of this study is to collect data from the experiences of people with [target population characteristics]. The data that will be collected through interviews and focus groups, will be analyzed to create the framework [for the development of a service/software] with [the purpose of]. The project aims to facilitate participants and people with [target population characteristics] in their interaction [this aspect of life]. At the same time, it aims to identify effective solutions together with individuals through their participation in collaborative and co-design activities. The co-design will take place in the [number of] workshops of the partners of the [project name] project consortium [(Country 1 – Partner 1, Country 2 – Partner 2 etc.)] providing information and suggestions for corrections and modifications regarding [aspect of life under study].

3. Study environment

The data for the study framework will be collected by the research team of the [project name] project, collaborators of the [partner 1 institution, research center 2 institution].

4. Timeline

The study will take place over a period [of duration], between [start date] and [end date].

5. Participants

The participants will be people who have been diagnosed with [syndrome, disorder, disease, healthy etc. – The target population]. These will be indicated by the study partners and their participation will take place under the conditions that they themselves have agreed and that the consent form is signed, [by them or their caregivers/legal representatives if applicable], allowing the collection and processing of data for the study purposes.

The criteria for inclusion of study participants are:

(a) [age criteria].

b) [diagnoses or difficulties which are part of the diagnoses]

c) have the intention to interact and share their experiences regarding the scenarios examined in the context of the [project name] project. These scenarios are related to [aspect of life concerned].

Regarding the exclusion criteria:

Persons outside the age group of [15-44 years] years will be excluded from participating in the study. People, who are likely to face difficulties during their participation such as [mention here difficulties], will be excluded. [In some cases, it may be desirable and useful for a participant's experiences to be provided on their behalf or assisted in their expression by a caregiver of the individual – if applicable].

Interviews / focus groups

Interviews/focus groups will be conducted in two phases, not necessarily with the participation of the same people. The participants of each phase will be:

- a) in the first phase, a total of [number of people] in interviews and focus groups (e.g. focus group of 15 people and 15 individual interviews) concerning [aspect of life]
- b) in the second phase, a total of [number of people] people in interviews / focus groups that will be held before and after using [the software/service], which aim to facilitate the [aspect of life], for the collection of evaluation data and feedback on the [software/service].

6. Data collection plan

The collection of the data will take place in the context of interviews / focus groups, during which, information will be collected on the usability of [software/services], common problems faced by [the target population] in its interaction with them and their requirements. Each interview is expected to last about [duration] and the focus group about [duration].

The interviews/focus groups may be recorded, and the recordings will be used solely for transcription of the data, without its further disclosure, and a pseudonymization process will follow. Transcripts from the [number of] interviews/ focus groups of the first phase will be sent, upon request, to the research team leading their analysis, [partner 1]. Transcripts from the [number of] interviews/ focus groups related to the [software/service] will be sent, upon request, [partner 1, research center 2].

Regarding the participation: a) the data collected will be solely used for the study purposes, while, in case they are used in published reports, outside the project context, they will be fully anonymized, b) the transcripts of the study will be carried out safely by the research team responsible for the project, and the resulting data will be [deleted/anonymized], on [date of data deletion/anonymization], c) the participants have the right to request for rectification or deletion of personal data at any time before their [deletion/anonymization] date and d) withdrawal from the interview is possible at any time, without requiring justification and without the legal rights of the departee being affected by it.

For more information on participating or to inform the research team of an impending departure from the study, please send an email to [Data Protection Officer email/contact details].

6.1. Data collection process through interview/focus group

The interviews / focus groups will take place [online and/or in person]. Initially, the participant will be welcomed, they will be reminded that their participation is voluntary and that their consent is necessary for the continuation of the process. After signing the consent form, the name of the participant will be converted into a code, which will be used from this point forward, and [the age, diagnosis, educational level, the city of residence, the profession, the period since the onset of their disorder – remove whatever is not applicable] will be collected.

Then, the interview / focus group will commence, stating that there are no wrong answers or views, that all opinions and experiences are acceptable and legitimate, and desirable to be heard. The researchers who will supervise / motivate / conduct and participate in the discussion, will take care, so that the discussion is not monopolized by a few participants, **in the case of a focus group.**

In the first phase of interviews / focus groups, participants will be invited to discuss the quality of [the aspect of life]. In the context of the discussion or interview, the challenges faced in [the aspect of life] and solutions that could offer improvements in it but also in their quality of life, will be analyzed and discussed.

In the second phase of the interviews / focus groups concerning the [software/service], the participants will have the opportunity to use it. This [software/service] will include [software/service content description]. The participants will have to interact with the [software/service] for a short period of time [some minutes], interacting freely with, while afterwards, they will also execute some tasks. Finally, they will have to express their opinion to the research team about the [software/service] functionality and the degree to which it helped them to interact, as well as to suggest possible modifications or additions.

The discussions and interviews that will take place are semi-structured, meaning that there is a precompiled interview draft (chapter 9), but both the interviewer or facilitator of the focus group may deviate from this structure, depending on the answers received and the course of the discussion, within the research design and purpose framework, as new questions are likely to arise, in order to achieve the unhindered expression of the thoughts, ideas and experiences of the participants.

Finally, the researchers will thank the participants.

7. Analyses

7.1. Description of data analysis

i) The analysis of the data collected in the first interviews / focus groups will take place in 3 stages: a) Content analysis of individual interviews and focus groups, b) Comparison and integration of content analysis in reports c) Comparison and integration of reports collected from the project consortium, in the overall project analysis report.

For the first step, the researchers will identify key topics of the discussions and recurring patterns that present and reflect problems faced by [the target population] and they will support their finding, e.g., quoting a phrase or excerpt from the conversation.

To complete the second step, the researchers will incorporate the findings into a report while in the third step, [Partner 1] will perform the same process, summarizing the individual reports of the partners.

ii) The analysis of the second phase interviews / focus groups data will be carried out in the context of the feedback received on the produced [software/service]. The interaction with the [software/service] and its use, through its pilot test, aims to result in a discussion with each participant, which will allow the [software/service] to be evaluated, and the possible issues that arise in its design and usability to be demonstrated. This will provide the [software/service] creators with the necessary and appropriate data, for the development of new improved versions through this co-creation process.

8. Provisions for the ethical conduct of the study

All participants will be informed through an information sheet, which will describe extensively and in a communicatively understandable way (to this audience) the overall study process. Their participation in the study will be made possible only after they provide their written consent, after being informed. The document used for this purpose is the '**Participant Informed Consent Form**'.

Specifically, they will be informed about the purpose of the study and that:

1. Their participation is voluntary and not obligatory.
2. They can ask any question about the study before deciding to participate in it.
3. They will be made aware of the individual and group benefits from their participation.
4. They will be informed of the exact way of collection, transfer and protection of sensitive personal data during the project, as well as its subsequent processing and utilization of these data, whether for example they will be deleted or reused, if such will be the case.
5. They will receive detailed and complete information, and that their consent is required for participating in the study, as well as for any further processing of their data.

6. They will be informed that they are able, at any time, to withdraw from the study or to request their data to be deleted, without consequences, and without affecting the services they receive by [their research doctor / health provider etc.].
7. Each participant's informed consent form will include the contact details of both the investigator's who conducted the briefing and those of the study principal investigator's.
8. The copy of the provided informed consent form will explicitly state that this information has been submitted to the [Research Ethics and Deontology Committee of [Partner 1]] beforehand and that all personal information and sensitive personal data will have been [pseudonymized with unique identification numbers / anonymized]

Appendices

Questionnaire – Interview / focus group guidelines

The interviews / focus groups will be based, but not restricted, on the following guidelines:

1. The date, time, location and number of the participants (if it is a focus group) of the meeting are noted.
2. The participants test the [software/service], provided by the research team.
3. The participants will interact with the [software/service], by performing free actions, but also specific tasks given by the research team.
4. The team will note difficulties and problems in using the [software/service].
5. Clarifying questions that stimulate the discussion, regarding [software/service] usability, will follow:
 - "Do you think the [service/software] facilitates your [aspect of life]?"
 - "Did you have difficulty using it? / If so, do you have anything specific to mention? / What were they? / How could they be improved?"
 - "What functions of the [service/software], do you think / consider / evaluate to be more useful and which ones less? / Why?"
 - "If you could add other function(s), what would they be?"

4.9.3.2 Protocol template for intervention studies

(for studies that do not involve medicines or medical devices according to EU 536/2014 & EU 2017/745-746)

(Highlighted text is present to provide examples. Please replace it to correspond to your study)

STUDY NAME:

Principal Investigator:

Contact information:

Data Protection Officer:

<p>1. Subject of the study and its objectives; state the hypotheses, separated into main and secondary hypotheses, and the clinical parameters (primary and secondary endpoints) against which the hypotheses will be tested</p>	<p>Study summary: Study Purpose: For this purpose, the study must be divided into sub-steps: Data acquisition, data collection, and statistical analysis. Data Acquisition: WHAT (end-points/outcome measures) is/are going to be measured</p>
--	--

	<p>Statistical analysis:</p> <p>Data will be analyzed using R/SPSS/Python/{name of other}. Name the statistic tests to be used for each category of data described above. A p-value below 0.05 is considered statistically significant.</p> <p>Hypotheses:</p> <p>Hypothesis 1:</p> <p>Hypothesis 2:</p> <p>...</p>
<p>2. Study timeline</p>	<p>Recruitment starts: D/M/YYYY</p> <p>Recruitment ends: D/M/YYYY</p> <p>Last participant exits: D/M/YYYY</p> <p>Data analysis starts: D/M/YYYY</p> <p>Data analysis ends: D/M/YYYY</p> <p>Or estimated period e.g., October 2020 till May 2023</p>
<p>3. Explanation of the significance of the study</p>	
<p>4. Which of the following regulations, laws, codes of conduct or other apply</p>	<p>a) EU 679/2016</p> <p>b) Declaration of Helsinki</p> <p>c) The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, 2017</p> <p>d) OTHER (e.g., EU 745/2017, 536/2014, national implementations of GDPR etc.)</p>
<p>5. Description of the planned measures/examination methods and any deviations from the measures/examinations commonly used in medical practice (what is "routine", what is done differently in the study?)</p> <p>-If validated questionnaires are used for study purposes, please indicate the name of the questionnaires and where they are published (references).</p> <p>-Please attach non-validated questionnaires.</p>	<p>Describe what the study entails and what is going to be measured</p> <p>Data collection: HOW, WHEN, WHERE, STORAGE</p> <p>Questionnaire #1, reference</p> <p>Questionnaire #2, reference</p> <p>...</p> <p>Attach non-validated questionnaires as appendix</p>
<p>6. Evaluation and weighing of the foreseeable risks and disadvantages of study participation against the</p>	<p>Remove row if not applicable (e.g., use of questionnaires)</p>

expected benefits for the study participants and persons who will become ill in the future (risk-benefit balance).	
a. Medical benefit to be tested for the study participants (individual benefit for the individual patient).	Remove row if not applicable (e.g. use of questionnaires) (e.g., There is no individual benefit to the study participants from completing the questionnaire.)
b. Medical benefit to be tested for persons with the disease in the future (group benefit).	What is the benefit to society/patients/future patients if the proposed study is successful
c. Risks and burdens to study participants (list all in detail).	List of risks or There are no risks for the study participants.
7. Measures to control risks	List of measures or There are no risks for the study participants.
8. Termination criteria	e.g., Recruitment numbers have been reached, project duration is up
9. Number, age, and sex of the persons concerned	
10. Power analysis with indication of statistical methodology, including justification of the number of cases. Specification of the statistician (if applicable)	WHO is going to perform the analysis (e.g., researcher, physician or NAME SURNAME of statistician) A power analysis was performed to estimate the sample size. At $\alpha=0.05$ and power= 0.80 , the extrapolated sample size required to detect a small effect (Cohen $d=0.2$) for between/within-group comparisons was $N=787$. Therefore, the inclusion of at least 787 subjects was deemed necessary.
11. a. Presentation and explanation of the inclusion and exclusion criteria , if applicable	
b. Study information (who gives verbally and in writing an indication of how much time is left between information and consent (written information as an attachment)?)	Who informs the participants. How much time is left between information and consent
c. Declaration of consent (written form as attachment)	The information sheet and consent form is attached to this application. Each participant receives a copy of the information sheet and the consent form.

d. If applicable, information and consent of the legal representative (if applicable, also description of the procedure for the establishment of judicial care for subjects unable to consent).	Remove row if not applicable
12. Measures to recruit study participants (notice board, newspaper advertisements, etc.)	
13. If applicable: reason for inclusion and demonstration of therapeutic benefit for individuals who are minors and/or unable to consent.	Remove row if not applicable
14. Relationship between study participant and study researcher/physician (is the study physician also the treating physician?).	Remove row if not applicable
15. Statement on the involvement of persons possibly dependent on the sponsor.	Remove row if not applicable
16. Measures that allow a determination of whether a study participant is participating in multiple studies at the same time or before the expiration of a period specified in the previous study. Is participation in multiple studies possible?	Remove row if not applicable
17. If applicable: remuneration or reimbursement of study participants (amount, for what should be paid?)	Remove row if not applicable
18. If applicable: insurance of the study participants (confirmation of insurance and insurance conditions, insurer, scope of insurance, duration of insurance).	The study is covered by the public/private liability insurance of the [name_of_insurance_provider]. Remove row if not applicable.
19. Documentation procedure: -Reference to CRF sheets, if applicable -Indication of the data to be collected -Sample handling	The research data collected from the patient/participant will be digitized into REDCap/OpenClinica/Other server using specific codes/standards which is located in [institution/(cloud)storage provider]-internal servers and kept for X years/months, after which the data will be anonymized/deleted.

<p>-Retention/archiving (incl. deadlines)</p> <p>-Access to the data and/or samples</p>	<p>WHO will have access?</p>
<p>20. If applicable: description of how the health status of healthy affected persons is to be documented</p>	<p>Remove row if not applicable</p>
<p>21. If applicable: methods to identify, document and report adverse events (when, by whom and how?)</p>	<p>Remove row if not applicable</p>
<p>22. Procedure to protect the confidentiality of stored data, documents, and, if applicable, samples, presentation of pseudonymization or anonymization of data, and samples of study participants (initials and date of birth as coding scheme are not allowed!).</p> <p>-Description of the separation of medical records, study documentation, and allocation of personal data.</p> <p>-Identification of access rights, including access to participant identification lists, during and after study implementation.</p> <p>-Detailed indication of the procedures for transmission, encryption, restriction of processing (blocking) and deletion (including an indication of the network structure used, if any, and servers used).</p> <p>-If necessary, access to identifying data for legally authorized auditors (third parties) for purpose-bound inspection of the files required for this purpose.</p>	<p>Strict compliance with EU 2016/679 (or other national laws) is ensured.</p> <p>Provide information according to the list on the left row</p>
<p>23. Declaration of compliance with data protection.</p> <p>-Assurance that all data collected and stored about the study participant will be treated confidentially</p>	<p>Participating physicians of the [LOCATION] are obliged to observe data secrecy and medical confidentiality. Researchers have signed Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDA). The data will not be passed on to third parties.</p>

<p>(data secrecy and medical confidentiality).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Assurance that the identifying data are accessible only to the study director or to employees authorized by the study director. -Indication of the measures taken to ensure confidentiality. -Measures for the data-protection-compliant transfer of data that do not allow third parties to establish a personal reference. -Information on the rights of data subjects. -Measures to ensure the rights of participants. <p>-If transfers to non-EU countries are planned: Are data protection compliance measures in place (e.g., existence of an adequacy decision by the EU Commission or explicit consent of study participants to such transfers)?</p>	<p>e.g., pseudonymization, appointment of DPO, access control, encryption and more</p>
<p>24. Names and addresses of the institutions involved in the study as study centers or study laboratories, as well as the study directors and the study physicians.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specification of involved external service provider with indication of data access possibility. 	<p>Include applicable roles:</p> <p>Study Director/Principal Investigator:</p> <p>Researchers:</p> <p>Physicians:</p> <p>Statistician:</p> <p>Other:</p> <p>Name and address of institution(s):</p>
<p>25. Information on the suitability of the trial site, in particular, on the adequacy of the resources and facilities available there, as well as on the personnel available to conduct the clinical trial and on experience in conducting similar trials.</p>	<p>The department of [LOCATION] and the scientists involved in this project have many years of experience in academic work and publications in high-ranking medical and technical journals.</p> <p>e.g., The [lab/Department/centre/other] is one of the most research-intensive departments at [LOCATION/UNIVERSITY etc.] and one of the most research-intensive [LAB/Department/centre/other] in [COUNTRY].</p>
<p>26. Agreement on access of the investigator/principal investigator/leader of the study</p>	<p>Publication policy:</p>

<p>to the data and the principles on publication. - Publications in a form that does not allow any conclusions to be drawn about the person.</p>	<p>Declaration that data included in publication are aggregates.</p> <p>[Only for VITALISE TA] Data Access and Publication policy is described in the “VITALISE Agreement for Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures” and the “VITALISE Transnational Bilateral User Agreement” signed by the Living Lab infrastructure provider and the Transnational Access user.</p>
<p>27. Information on the funding of the study: funding source (name and location) and amount of funding in €.</p>	

4.9.3.3 Template for Data Sharing Agreement / Joint-Controller Agreement

Data Sharing Agreement / Joint-Controller Agreement

Version 1.0 as of [month, year]

“[Research project full name]”
 (“the Project”),

[(if a Grant Agreement is in place)
 as identified in the Grant Agreement]
 [project number – short name]

Between

[name of Living Lab 1]
 [name of Living Lab 2]
 ...
 [name of Living Lab 3]

Parties to the Agreement

This Agreement is between:

Organisation / Living Lab	Represented by
European Network of Living Labs (ENOLL)	[Insert name, surname and job title here of person with the signing authority for the

	organization e.g., CEO, President, Rector etc.]

The Parties are acting as joint controllers on behalf of the [short name] research project which has received funding from [funding authority/programme] under [Grant/Bilateral/Other] Agreement No [project number], entitled: “[Project full name]”.

The Parties agree to share the Personal Data on terms set out in this Agreement which explains the purposes for which that Personal Data may be used.

In the context of the specific project, all parties can act as data providers and/or data recipients.

AGREED TERMS

1. INTERPRETATION

The following definitions and rules of interpretation apply in this agreement.

Definitions:

Privacy and Data Protection Legislation: The national data protection legislation, the Human Rights Act 1998, the European Convention on Human Rights, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; EU 2016/679) and all applicable laws and regulations relating to the processing of the personal data and privacy, and the equivalent of any of the foregoing in any relevant jurisdiction. References to legislation include any amendments made to those laws from time to time.

The Project: The [project short name] project.

Agreed Purposes: has the meaning given to it in Clause 3 of this Agreement.

The Agreement: this Agreement.

Business Day: a day other than a Saturday, Sunday or public holiday in the countries of each Party when banks are open for business.

The Tasks: the tasks the Parties are contracted to carry out under the [Grant/Bilateral/Other] Agreement No [project number] in order to provide the relevant deliverables.

Joint Controllers: According to Article 26(1) GDPR where two or more controllers jointly determine the purposes and means of processing of personal data, they shall be joint controllers.

Data provider: means the Party acting as joint controller, whose role in the Project involves the provision of personal data to the Project, including data transferring to the Data Recipients, for the purposes and tasks set out in [project number] and further specified in Appendix I to this Agreement.

Data recipient(s): means one (or more) of the Parties, acting as joint controller(s), whose role in the Project involves research and analysis on personal data provided to the Project by the Data Provider, for the purposes and tasks set out in the [reference in the project] of the Project [Grant/Bilateral/Other] Agreement No [project number] and further specified in Appendix I to this Agreement.

Data Processor: means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of a controller.

Lead Data Protection Authority: the supervisor authority of the Data Provider.

The Data Protection Authorities Concerned: the supervisor authorities of the Data Recipients.

The Personal Data: means personal data as defined in the GDPR, any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person, including [define personal data here or in an Appendix] and to be shared between the parties under Clause 4 of this Agreement.

Subject Access Request: means the "Right of access by the data subject" in Article 15 of the GDPR.

Term: shall mean the duration of the data sharing agreement which shall remain in force for the duration of the Project, but until [date], unless an extension of the Project duration is granted by the [funding authority].

Data Subject, Personal Data, sensitive/special category data, pseudonymisation, anonymisation, personal data breach, processing, supervisory authority and appropriate technical and organisational measures shall have the meanings given to them in Article 4 of the GDPR.

Clause, Appendix and paragraph headings shall not affect the interpretation of this Agreement.

The Appendices form part of this Agreement and shall have effect as if set out in full in the body of this Agreement. Any reference to this Agreement includes the Appendices.

Unless the context requires otherwise, words in the singular shall include the plural and, in the plural, shall include the singular.

References to Clauses and Appendices are to the Clauses and Appendices of this Agreement and references to paragraphs are to paragraphs of the relevant Appendix.

Any words following the terms including, include, in particular or for example or any similar phrase shall be construed as illustrative and shall not limit the generality of the related general words.

A reference to **writing** or **written** includes letter, fax and email.

2. COMPLIANCE WITH DATA PROTECTION LAWS

2.1 The Parties acknowledge that under the GDPR, the Parties are acting as Joint Controllers where processing Personal Data under the terms of this Agreement.

2.2 Each Party must ensure compliance with the Privacy and Data Protection Legislation at all times during the Term of the Agreement.

3. AGREED PURPOSES

3.1 This Agreement sets out the framework for the sharing of Personal Data between the Parties. It sets out the purposes for which the Parties, the principles may process the Personal data and procedures that the Parties shall adhere to and the respective responsibilities of the Parties, in a transparent manner.

3.2 In order to carry out the tasks set under the [Grant/Bilateral/Other] Agreement No [project number] the Parties have to transfer Personal Data between the Parties. Appendix I to this Agreement provides a detailed outline of the Purposes and Tasks and how the personal data will be processed to carry out those Tasks related to the purposes of the project.

3.3 The Parties agree to only process the Personal data in accordance with the instructions set out in this Agreement, and only for the purposes of performing the Tasks as described in Appendix I. The Parties shall not process Personal Data in a way that is incompatible with the purposes described in this Clause (the Agreed Purposes).

3.4 Each party shall appoint a single point of contact (SPoC) who will work together to reach an agreement with regards to any issues arising from the data sharing and to actively improve the effectiveness of the data sharing agreement. The points of contact for each of the parties are:

List of Single Point of Contact persons

[Parties, contact persons, contact information]

4. **PERSONAL DATA**

4.1 The Personal Data shared under this Agreement are [define personal data here or in Appendix III]

4.2 The Parties agree that the Personal Data shared under this Agreement must be pseudonymized by the Data Provider before transferring to Data Recipients and not be irrelevant or excessive with regard to the Agreed Purposes set out in Clause 3, in order to minimise the amount of Personal Data shared, in accordance with the Data Minimisation Principle.

4.3 The Data Recipients agree to process the Personal Data described in [Clause 4.1 or Appendix III], only for the purposes outlined in Clause 3 of this Agreement and strictly for no other purpose without the written authority of the Data Provider.

4.4 The Data Recipients will NOT disclose or share the Personal Data processed under the Agreement, with any third party without the written authority of the Data Provider.

4.5 The Data Recipients are prohibited from publishing any information related or produced by the Personal Data shared, including any results, without prior authorisation by the **Data Provider**.

5. **FAIR, TRANSPARENT AND LAWFUL PROCESSING**

5.1 Each Party shall ensure that it processes the Personal Data in a fair, transparent and lawful manner in accordance with the Privacy and Data Protection Legislation during the Term of this Agreement.

5.2 For the purposes of processing collected data from [project short name] users, as described in Appendix I, to this Agreement, each Party shall ensure that it processes shared Personal Data on the basis of the following legal grounds:

- a. Lawful processing is based on the data subjects' consent according to Article 6(1a) of the GDPR and/or
- b. Lawful processing is based on the public interest and/or
- c. Lawful processing is based on the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the joint controllers.

[Define the appropriate basis for lawful processing]

5.3 For the purposes described in Clause 5.2 of this Agreement, the Data Provider undertakes to inform, where applicable, the data subjects with the information listed in Article 13 of the GDPR in order to comply with the principle of transparency.

6. **DATA ACCURACY**

6.1 The Parties agree to ensure that the Personal Data processed is accurate and kept up to date. The Parties agree to review the accuracy of the personal data and make any necessary changes to any Personal Data, which is inaccurate or requires updating.

6.2 Where either Party becomes aware of inaccuracies in shared Personal Data, they will notify the other Parties.

7. **RETENTION PERIOD**

7.1 The Parties shall retain the personal data of data subjects for [define the retention period of data as well as whether they shall be anonymised or deleted afterwards].

8. **DATA SUBJECTS' RIGHTS**

8.1 For the purposes of processing collected data from [project short name] users based on the legal grounds of Clause 5.2 of this Agreement, the Data Subjects are entitled to the following rights:

- a. The right to be informed, the right of access, the right to rectification, the right to data portability and the right to withdraw consent.

b. In case the consent is withdrawn, the Parties have the obligation to erase the Personal Data that was processed, unless there is another purpose justifying the continued retention . In this case and in line with Articles 7(3), 17(1b), 17(3d) and 89 of the GDPR, the processing of Personal Data necessary for scientific research purposes or for the purposes of archiving in the public interest may be used to justify the retention of the Personal Data.

c. Any change in the lawful basis for processing must be notified to a Data Subject in accordance with the information requirements in Articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR and under the general principle of transparency.

8.2 Data Subjects can exercise their rights through a Subject Access Request to the Data Provider. If required, the Data Recipients agree to provide full co-operation and assistance to the Data Provider to enable him to comply with Subject Access Requests and to respond to any other queries or complaints. The Data Recipients agree to provide such assistance promptly and no later than [N] Business Days upon receipt by the Data Provider of a Data Subject request.

8.3 In case of any Subject Access Requests, queries or complaints received by the Data Recipients, the Data Recipients shall notify the Data Provider immediately (and no later than [define time period]) upon receipt in order to enable the Data Provider to respond promptly to the Data Subjects.

8.4 The Data Recipients agree to act only under the Data Provider's instructions in relation to any activities undertaken to resolve any complaints or comply with any requests from the Data Subjects under Clause 7.

8.5 To facilitate the Data Subjects' rights, the Parties agree to maintain Records of all Personal Data processed and all processing activities under the Agreement (including any processing activities outsourced to a Data Processor, see Clause 8) in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable form. In addition to the above Records, the Parties shall maintain a record of Subject Access Requests or complaints including the decisions made or measures taken and any information that was exchanged. The Data Provider reserves the right to inspect the records maintained by the Data Recipients under this Clause at any time.

9. **THIRD PARTY ACCESS**

List of third parties

[Legal name, Address, Country] [has appointed a DPO/has a privacy policy in place (link)] and will process the following personal data under commercial terms & conditions: [Personal data 1, Personal data 2, Personal data 3]. All data accessed by [Legal name] will be pseudonymized. Participants will be informed of this third-party access and will have given consent before said access is performed.

10. **DATA TRANSFERS OUTSIDE THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AREA (EEA)**

[List the recipients of personal data outside the EEA and the technical and organisational measures taken or contractual clauses or adequacy decision in place.]

[Legal name, Address, Country] The European Commission published an adequacy decision for the [Country], for the purposes of Art. 45 of EU 2016/679, on [date of decision] which will last, unless renewed, until [date of EC decision's termination].

11. **SECURITY**

11.1 The Parties shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to protect the Personal Data shared, in particular from accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to Personal Data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed in accordance with Article 32 of the GDPR.

11.2 Specifically, taking into account the Agreed Purposes and Processing activities (Clause 3), the nature of the Personal Data shared (Clause 4), the state of the art, the costs of implementation, as well as the risks arising from such processing activities for the rights and freedoms of the Data

subjects, the Parties shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to those risks, including but not limited to the measures specified in Appendix II to this Agreement. The Parties agree to assist each other in meeting their obligation to keep the Personal Data shared secure and notify each other of any changes to the measures described in Appendix II.

11.3 The Data Recipients agree to allow for inspections and assessments to be undertaken by the Data Provider in respect of the security measures taken, or to provide evidence of those measures if requested.

12. DATA PROTECTION IMPACT ASSESSMENT (DPIA)

12.1 The Data Recipients as Joint Controllers with the Data Provider shall provide assistance to the Data Provider in meeting Article 35 obligation of the GDPR, if required, to carry out a joint Data Protection Impact Assessment, in relation to Processing of the Personal Data shared and taking into account any future changes on the risks represented by processing operations that might require a review of the original Data Protection Impact Assessment.

12.2 Where a DPIA referred to Clause 12.1 indicates an unmitigated high risk to the processing operations, the Data Recipients shall assist the Data Provider in meeting the Prior Consultation obligation with its Supervisory Authority in accordance of Article 36 of the GDPR.

13. PERSONAL DATA BREACHES AND REPORTING PROCEDURES

13.1 The Data Recipients are under a strict obligation to immediately notify the Data Provider of any Personal Data Breach and no later than 24 hours upon the Data Recipients' becoming aware of the breach. The Data Recipients shall provide all available information for the breach in order to enable the Data Provider to assess the risks to the rights and freedoms of the Data subjects and the actions required to resolve the issue in accordance with the Privacy and Data Protection Legislation and guidelines.

13.2 In case the Personal Data Breach is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of the Data Subjects, the Data Recipients shall provide full assistance in order for the Data Provider to notify its Supervisory Authority within 72 hours, and if required, to notify the affected Data Subjects. Taking into account the conditions of the breach and the security measures applied, the Supervisor Authority might decide that a communication of the breach to the Data Subjects, in line with Article 34 of the GDPR, is not required.

13.3 The Data Recipients shall assist the Data Provider to document any Personal Data Breaches, comprising the facts relating to the security breaches, its effects and the remedial action taken to enable the Supervisory Authority to verify compliance with Article 33 of the GDPR.

14. DOCUMENTATION OF COMPLIANCE AND AUDIT RIGHTS

14.1 Upon request by the Data Provider, the Data Recipients shall make available to the Data Provider all relevant information needed to demonstrate that they are all meeting the requirements of the GDPR, and reasonably cooperate with audits, including inspections by the Data Provider or an auditor mandated by the Data Provider or a competent Supervisory Authority. In order to be able to demonstrate compliance the Parties shall maintain appropriate records as described in Clauses 8.5 and 13.3.

14.2 The Data Provider shall give notice of any audit or inspection to be conducted to a Data Recipient and shall make reasonable endeavours to avoid causing damage or disruption to the Data Recipient's premises, equipment and work in the course of such an audit or inspection.

14.3 The Data Recipients must inform immediately the Data Provider in case they think they have been given an instruction, which does not comply with the Privacy and Data Protection Legislation.

15. TERMINATION

15.1 The Parties agree that following expiration or termination of this Agreement, the Data Recipients and any Processor acting on behalf of a Data recipient shall, at the choice of the Data Provider, return all the Personal Data transferred and the copies thereof to the Data Provider or shall destroy all the personal data and certify to the Data Provider that they have done so, unless legislation imposed upon a Data Recipient or any Processor prevents them from returning or destroying all or part of the Personal Data transferred. In that case, the Data Recipients or any Processor engaged must warrant that they shall guarantee the confidentiality of the personal data transferred and shall not actively process the personal data transferred anymore. The terms of this Agreement will continue to apply to such Personal Data.

15.2 The Data Provider reserves the right to issue instructions to be followed by the Data Recipients including any Processors for the destruction of the Personal Data shared under Clause 15.1, at any time.

16. LIMITATION OF LIABILITY

16.1 Nothing in this Agreement relieves the Data Providers and Data recipients as joint controllers of their own direct responsibilities and liabilities under the GDPR.

17. SEVERANCE

17.1 If any provision or part-provision of the Agreement is or becomes invalid, illegal or unenforceable, it shall be deemed modified to the minimum extent necessary to make it valid, legal and enforceable. If such modification is not possible, the relevant provision or part-provision shall be deemed deleted. Any modification to or deletion of a provision or part-provision under this clause shall not affect the validity and enforceability of the rest of this agreement.

18. CHANGES TO THE APPLICABLE LAW

18.1 In case the applicable data protection and ancillary laws change in a way that the Agreement is no longer adequate for the purpose of governing lawful data sharing exercises, the Data Provider reserves the right to amend this Agreement. In such circumstances, the Data Recipients agree to implement any changes to its processing activities as are necessary to comply with the amended terms of the Agreement.

19. FORCE MAJEURE

19.1 Neither Party shall be in breach of this Agreement nor liable for delay in performing, or failure to perform, any of its obligations under this Agreement if such delay or failure result from events, circumstances or causes beyond its reasonable control. In such circumstances, the affected party shall be entitled to a reasonable extension of the time for performing such obligations. If the period of delay or non-performance continues for 3 months, the Party not affected may terminate this Agreement by giving 30 days' written notice to the affected Party.

20. GOVERNING LAW AND DISPUTE RESOLUTION

20.1 This Agreement shall be governed by GDPR. The Clauses shall be governed by the law of the Member State in which the Data provider is established. The Parties will firstly seek to resolve any disputes arising in connection with this Agreement by amicable settlement. The Parties shall abide by a decision of a competent court or of the Lead Supervisory Authority of the Data Provider's country of establishment.

Appendix I – Purposes and Tasks

[Short description of the research project (purpose) with focus in personal data processing (tasks)]

Appendix II – Description of the Security Measures

[Describe security measures for data protection implemented by each party such as Pseudonymisation, Encryption, back-up procedures, Audit Log operation, non-disclosure agreements, non-reidentification declaration, ISO27001 etc]

Appendix III – Description of Personal Data

[Description of what personal data is to be processed in the research project]

SIGNATURES

AS WITNESS:

Each person signing below and each Party on whose behalf such person executes this Agreement warrants that he/she, as the case may be, has the authority and the legal capacity to enter into this Agreement and perform the obligation herein.

The Parties have caused this Data Sharing Agreement to be duly signed by the undersigned authorised representatives in separate signature pages the day and year first above written.

[Organisation/Living Lab 1]

Signature:

Name:

Position:

Date:

[Organisation/Living Lab 2]

Signature:

Name:

Position:

Date:

4.10 PART 7B. Devices and technologies

This Part presents a taxonomy for identifying and classifying the data that are collected in Living Lab environments and consequently link the devices that are used for collecting each data category. The aim of the taxonomy is to help finding the appropriate digital data collection tools for living lab research and/or expand understanding about available tools and their possibilities. Furthermore, the taxonomy aims to facilitate data collection by driving a unified representation schema of the collected datasets enabling the the cross-organizational collaboration and the accessibility of Living Labs to external stakeholders.

Table 13 Devices and technologies provided by Living Labs

			Definition
Categories of devices for data monitoring and collection	Environmental monitoring		characterize and monitor the environment, establish environmental parameters and conditions. As environment we refer to the person's surroundings either indoors or outdoors
	Human monitoring	Biometrics	biological measurements — or physical characteristics — that can be used to identify individuals and their unique characteristics such as fingerprint scanning or voice recognition

		Electrical Biosignals and physiological monitoring measures	electrical biosignals, or bioelectrical time signals, usually refers to the change in electric current produced by the sum of an electrical potential difference across a specialized tissue, organ or cell system like the nervous system
		(Primary) Vital signs	a group of the six most important medical signs that indicate the status of the body's vital function according to HL7 standard
		Body size and composition	measurement of a person's body, used as qualifying elements for vital signs
		Cognitive ability and mental processes	Measuring the processes involved in the acquisition of knowledge, reasoning and management of information and the brain-based skills we need to carry out any task
		Activity and behavioral monitoring	monitoring the individuals' physical activities and tracking their performance. Monitoring behavior and activities of daily living (ADLs)
Categories of technologies for interventions	Assistive Technology		technologies used to increase, maintain, or improve the functional capabilities of individuals, the feeling of autonomy, safety and general wellbeing or also supporting participation.
	Extended reality - XR (VR & AR)		allows for a two-way flow of information through an interface between the user and the technology through a simulated experience that can be similar to or completely different from the real world
	Serious Games		all the digital games that are used as interventions for health and wellbeing not including XR

Table 14 Devices and technologies subcategories

Category	Subcategory
Environment monitoring	Concentration levels (air pollution levels, humidity, atmospheric pressure, air quality)
	Technical alerts (e.g., flood, smoke)
	Environmental Temperature (air or water temperature)
	Luminosity
	Audiovisual devices
Biometrics	Face recognition
	Voice recognition
Electrical Biosignals and physiological monitoring measures	EEG (electroencephalography)
	ECG (electrocardiography)
	EMG (electromyography)
	Vo2 (maximal oxygen consumption)
	Blood oxygen
	Blood sugar level
	GSR (galvanic skin response)
(Primary) Vital signs	Diastolic blood pressure
	Systolic blood pressure
	Heart rate
	Body temperature
	Respiratory rate
	Oxygen saturation
Body size and composition	body height - lying (measure on a horizontal surface)
	body weight
	body measures (fat, mass, muscle, water and bone)
	circumference measures (head, neck, biceps, waist, hip, chest, forearm, thigh and calf)
	Body Mass Index
Cognitive ability and mental processes	cognitive tasks and paradigms
	memory
	processing speed
	attention
Activity and behavioral monitoring and tracking	walking speed
	orientation

	human body location (indoors or outdoors)
	movement monitoring
	human balance
	physical activity level
	physical performance
	sleep
	steps
	stress level
	physical performance
	technology usage habits and patterns
	fall detection
	gesture recognition and detection
Assistive Technology	reminders & alert
	coaching
	training
	walk assistance
	support activities of daily living (ADLs)
	natural language understanding
Extended reality – XR (VR & AR)	Virtual reality (VR)
	Augmented reality (AR)
Serious Games	cognitive gaming
	physical gaming - exergames
	educational games

4.11 PART 7C Validated Questionnaires and instruments

The following tables summarize the questionnaires and instruments utilized during the JRA pilots, categorized in four (4) main axes: 1) Health Status & Wellbeing, 2) Cognitive Status, 3) Physical Activity/Mobility, and 4) Usability & User Experience Measures.

Table 15 Health Status & Wellbeing questionnaires and instruments

Health status & Wellbeing	
Variable measured	Tool
Quality of life	WHOQOL
Quality of life/Health status	EuroQol (EQ-5D)
	12-Item Short Form Survey (SF-12)

	36-Item Short Form Survey (SF-36)
	PROMIS-29
Mental wellbeing/Distress	Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9)
	Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS)
	Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS)
	State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI)
	General Anxiety Disorder Assessment (GAD7)
	Beck Depression Inventory (BDI)
	Short Anxiety Screening Test (SAST)
	Stress Visual Analog Scale (VAS Stress)
Mental wellbeing/self-efficacy	General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE-6)
Loneliness and Isolation	University of California Los Angeles Loneliness Scale (UCLA 3-item)
	Lubben Social Network Scale (LSNS-6)
Fatigue	Multidimensional Fatigue Inventory (MFI)
Pain	Pain Visual Analog Scale (VAS Pain)
Autonomy & Control / Functional status	Lawton Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (Lawton IADL)
Frailty	Clinical Frailty Scale (CFS)
Mortality prediction	Charlson Comorbidity Index (CCI)

Table 16 Cognitive status questionnaires and instruments

Cognitive status	
Variable measured	Tool
Multiple cognitive processes/Cognitive impairment	Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA)

Multiple cognitive processes/Cognitive impairment	Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE)
Attention and Processing skills	Stroop Test
Language/Naming ability	Boston Naming Test
Verbal learning and Memory	Hopkins Verbal Learning Test (HVLT)
Attention, sequencing, visual search, psychomotor speed	Trail A + B
Working memory, attention, sequencing	Digit span (Forward and Backward)
Psychomotor speed	Symbol-Digit Modalities Test (SDMT)
Verbal learning and memory	Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Test
Executive cognitive function	Functional cognitive assessment scale (FUCAS)
Visual learning, delayed visual memory, recognition	Brief visuospatial memory test

Table 17 Physical Activity/Mobility questionnaires and instruments

Physical Activity/Mobility	
Variable measured	Tool
Motor function in stroke survivors	Fugl-Meyer Assessment
Intensity levels of physical activity	Community Healthy Activities Model Program for Seniors (CHAMPS)
	Borg Perceived exertion Scale
Time spent for different levels physical activity	International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ)
Physical activity level, strength, flexibility	Rapid Assessment of Physical Activity (RAPA)
Persons' perception of balance and stability during activities of daily living and their fear of falling	Tinetti-test
Static balance and fall risk	Berg Balance Scale (BBS)
Leg strength and endurance	30" Chair Stand Test

Lower body flexibility	Chair sit-and-reach test
Fall risk and the progress of balance, sit to stand and walking	Timed Up & Go (TUG)
Aerobic capacity and endurance	2-Minute Step test
	6 Minute Walk Test
Self-paced walking ability and functional capacity	2 Minute Walk Test
Speed in meters per second	10 Metre Walk Test
Static postural and balance control	Balance on one leg / Single leg Stance test
Finger dexterity	9-hole peg test
Balance and gait while backwards walking	Backward walking test
Upper body and shoulder flexibility	Back scratch test
Upper body strength and overall strength	Hand grip strength
Upper body strength and endurance	Arm curl test

Table 18 Usability & User experience questionnaires and instruments

Usability & User experience	
Variable measured	Tool
Usability	System Usability Scale (SUS)
User experience	User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ)
Intervention acceptability	Acceptability of Intervention Measure (AIM)
Intervention appropriateness	Intervention Appropriateness Measure (IAM)
Intervention feasibility	Feasibility of Intervention Measure (FIM)
Usability	UMUX-LITE
Feasibility and Acceptability	Feasibility and Acceptability Questionnaire
User satisfaction	Quebec User Evaluation of Satisfaction with Assistive Technology (QUEST 2.0)

5 Conclusion

This document presents information about the collection of data and analysis towards the creation of the Standard Version 0.5 for Living Labs in the Health and Wellbeing domain. Although the name of this deliverable is Standard version 5, the authors decided to name the Standard v0.5 as not all the parts have undergone Harmonization process yet. From the work that has been done so far, the authors concluded that there are various domains that will benefit from the Harmonization processes and that there is need for Harmonization in various contexts (Section 4.1). Standard Version 0.5 is an improved and updated version of 0.4. There is still some missing information for specific sections which will be included during the upcoming final standard version, however, as we approach the conclusion of the VITALISE project, all Standard parts are in a partially completed state. Important adjustments of this Standard Version were integrated into Part 2, which underwent a name change from "Living Lab Business Model" to "Living Lab Governance and Business Model." Within this segment, we outline the value proposition for Living Labs, present the latest version of Living Lab Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and introduce a new segment focusing on the Living Lab Research and Innovation process as an integral element of the Living Lab Governance model. Additionally, revisions were made in Part 7, addressing Living Lab methods and tools. These modifications include the incorporation of tools for supporting ethical submission applications and the initial categorization of validated Living Lab questionnaires. The process will continue for one more semester and its results will be released by the end of the project (M36). The VITALISE consortium envisions to create a methodology that will continue to evolve even after the end of the project and that will be adopted by other thematic areas Living Labs (e.g., urban Living Labs) to capture the particularities of each domain and to identify the similarities across Living Lab practices.

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